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Distinct regulation of early trafficking of the NMDA receptors by the ligand-binding domains of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits

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1 **Title:** Distinct regulation of early trafficking of the NMDA receptors by the ligand-binding domains
2 of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits

3 **Running title:** Regulation of NMDARs by ligand-binding domains

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40

41 **Abstract**

42 N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) play a crucial role in excitatory neurotransmission,
43 with numerous pathogenic variants identified in the GluN subunits, including their ligand-binding
44 domains (LBDs). The prevailing hypothesis postulates that the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) quality
45 control machinery verifies the agonist occupancy of NMDARs, but this was tested in a limited
46 number of studies. Using microscopy and electrophysiology in the HEK293 cells, we found that
47 surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors containing a set of alanine substitutions within the
48 LBDs correlated with the measured EC_{50} values for glycine (GluN1 subunit mutations), while did
49 not correlate with the measured EC_{50} values for L-glutamate (GluN2A subunit mutations). The
50 mutant cycle of GluN1-S688 residue, including the pathogenic GluN1-S688Y and GluN1-S688P
51 variants, showed a correlation between relative surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2A
52 receptors and the measured EC_{50} values for glycine, as well as with the calculated $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values
53 for glycine obtained from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. In contrast, the mutant cycle of
54 GluN2A-S511 residue did not show any correlation between the relative surface expression of
55 the GluN1/GluN2A receptors and the measured EC_{50} values for L-glutamate or calculated $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$
56 values for L-glutamate. Co-expression of both mutated GluN1 and GluN2A subunits led to additive
57 or synergistic alterations in the surface number of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. The synchronized
58 ER release by ARIAD technology confirmed the altered early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A
59 receptors containing the mutated LBDs. The microscopical analysis from embryonal rat
60 hippocampal neurons (both sexes) corroborated our conclusions from the HEK293 cells.

61

62 **Significant statement**

63 We examined >80 mutant GluN1/GluN2 receptor combinations, including pathogenic and
64 potentially pathogenic variants in the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits. The combination of
65 the experimentally measured (relative surface expression, EC₅₀ values) and calculated ($\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$
66 values, RMSD, and SASA) parameters revealed that the LBDs of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits
67 distinctly regulate the early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. In addition, we validated a
68 novel system of synchronized release of GluN1/GluN2A receptors from the ER. Our findings
69 support the urgency of further detailed research on the regulation of early trafficking of NMDARs,
70 as it may open the avenue to targeted intervention of central nervous system disorders associated
71 with pathogenic variants in GluN subunits.

72

73 **Introduction**

74 *N*-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) are a family of ionotropic glutamate receptors that
75 play a crucial role in excitatory transmission in the mammalian central nervous system (CNS).
76 Conventional NMDARs are heterotetramers of two GluN1 and two GluN2 subunits in a 1-2-1-2
77 arrangement. Eight known splice variants of the GluN1 subunit arise from a single gene, and there
78 are four different genes for the GluN2 subunits: GluN2A, GluN2B, GluN2C, and GluN2D (Sanz-
79 Clemente et al., 2013; Vieira et al., 2020; Hansen et al., 2021). Each GluN subunit consists of
80 four membrane helices (M1-M4), an intracellular C-terminal domain (CTD), an extracellular
81 amino-terminal domain (ATD), and an extracellular loop between M3 and M4 (Figure 1A). The
82 ligand-binding domain (LBD) is formed by two segments, S1 and S2 (Traynelis et al., 2010;
83 Paoletti et al., 2013). Critical amino acid residues in the LBDs that are involved either by direct
84 interactions or via water molecules in the interaction with agonists (glycine in the GluN1 subunit
85 and L-glutamate in the GluN2 subunits, respectively) are highly conserved among mammals,
86 highlighting their critical importance for the proper function of NMDARs (Stroebel and Paoletti,
87 2021).

88 One of the critical parameters contributing to the physiological or pathophysiological roles
89 of NMDARs is their number on the cell surface, determined by the balance between their
90 exocytosis and endocytosis. Exocytosis (hereafter referred to as “early trafficking”) of NMDARs
91 is regulated at several levels. This includes control over their translation, the proper assembly of
92 functional heterotetramers and maturation in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), and intracellular
93 trafficking via Golgi apparatus (GA) (Meddows et al., 2001; Schüler et al., 2008; Horak et al.,
94 2014; Hanus and Ehlers, 2016). Alternative pathways bypassing the Golgi apparatus have also
95 been identified (Jeyifous et al., 2009). The prevailing hypothesis dealing with the processing of
96 NMDARs in the ER postulates that the ER quality control machinery verifies the sensitivity of

97 NMDARs to their (co)-agonists via a common mechanism shared with the α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-
98 methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid receptors (AMPA receptors) and kainate receptors (KARs) (Penn et al.,
99 2008; Coleman et al., 2009, 2010; Scholefield et al., 2019; Horak et al., 2021). However, in the
100 case of GluN1/GluN2 receptors, this hypothesis is supported by a relatively limited number of
101 studies, namely (i) on the mutant GluN1-D732A/GluN2A receptor, which shows virtually zero
102 surface expression and an extremely high EC₅₀ value for glycine due to disruption of direct glycine
103 interaction with GluN1-D732 residue (Kenny et al., 2009), (ii) GluN1/GluN2B receptors carrying
104 mutations that disrupt direct (GluN2B-E413A, GluN2B-S690G, GluN2B-R519K) and water
105 (GluN2B-V686A) interaction with L-glutamate or that indirectly lead to changes in EC₅₀ values for
106 L-glutamate (GluN2B-F416S) (She et al., 2012), and (iii) pathogenic variants in the LBDs of the
107 GluN2A and GluN2B subunits, specifically, that disrupt direct (GluN2B-E413G, GluN2A-R518H)
108 and water (GluN2A-G483R, GluN2A-V685G, GluN2A-D731N) interaction with L-glutamate or are
109 present elsewhere in the LBDs (GluN2A-T531M, GluN2B-C461F, GluN2A-I694T, GluN2A-
110 M705V, GluN2A-A716T, GluN2A-A727T, GluN2A-V734L, GluN2A-K772E) (Swanger et al.,
111 2016). However, our recent study showed that even a profound reduction in the EC₅₀ value for
112 glycine does not lead to a decrease in the surface number of GluN1-S688Y/GluN2 receptors
113 (Skrenkova et al., 2020), supporting further research addressing the roles of LBDs in the early
114 trafficking of GluN1/GluN2 receptors.

115 We investigated the early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors by mutagenesis of amino
116 acid residues in the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits involved in direct interaction with
117 agonists. Our experiments showed a statistically significant (for alanine substitutions in the GluN1
118 subunit) and no (for alanine substitution in the GluN2A subunit) correlation between surface
119 expression levels and EC₅₀ values for glycine or L-glutamate, respectively. In addition, co-
120 expression of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits with alanine substitutions additively or
121 synergically altered the surface numbers of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. The experimental and *in*
122 *silico* findings from the study of the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511 residues
123 revealed that the LBDs of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits distinctly regulate the early trafficking
124 of GluN1/GluN2A receptors.

125

126 **Materials and Methods**

127 *Molecular biology*

128 We used the following DNA vectors carrying genes encoding rat versions of the YFP-GluN1-1a
129 (NP_058706.1), GluN1-4a (NP_001257539.1), GluN2A or GFP-GluN2A (NP_036705), GluN2B
130 or GFP-GluN2B (NP_036706), GluN3A (NP_612555.1), human GluN2A (hGluN2A,

131 NP_001127879.1) subunits. Human versions of YFP-GluN1-1a (YFP-hGluN1-1a) and GluN1-4a
132 (hGluN1-4a) were prepared as we published previously (Skrenkova et al., 2020). The closed cleft
133 conformation of LBDs of the GluN1-4a (GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C) and GFP-GluN2A (GFP-
134 GluN2A-K487C-N687C) subunits were constructed according to previous studies (Blanke and
135 VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu, 2010; Dai and Zhou, 2016). An ARIAD-mNEONGreen-
136 GluN1-1a construct (ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a) containing the ARIAD sequence (Hangen et al.,
137 2018) followed by a rat version of the GluN1-1a subunit with an inserted mNEONGreen sequence
138 after the 21st amino acid residue was prepared by gene synthesis (Thermo Fischer Scientific)
139 and subsequently subcloned into the pcDNA3 expression vector. A human version of the ARIAD-
140 mNEONGreen-GluN1-1a construct (ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a) was made by introducing the
141 following amino acid substitutions: N159S, R212K, I267L, M415L. The specific amino acid
142 substitutions were performed using the QuikChange site-directed mutagenesis kit (Agilent
143 Technologies) and verified by DNA sequencing.

144

145 *HEK293 cells and primary hippocampal neurons*

146 Human embryonic kidney 293 (HEK293) cells were grown in Opti-MEM I medium supplemented
147 with 5% fetal bovine serum (FBS; both from Thermo Fischer Scientific) and used in experiments
148 up to passage 10. For electrophysiology, HEK293 cells in 24-well plates were transfected with a
149 total of 0.9 µg of DNA vectors carrying genes encoding GluN1 and GluN2 subunits and green
150 fluorescent protein (GFP; pQBI 25 vector; for identification of transfected cells; Takara) in a 1:1:1
151 ratio using 0.9 µl of PolyMag reagent (OZBiosciences) in 50 µl of Opti-MEM I medium. After 20
152 min incubation on a magnetic plate, HEK293 cells were trypsinized and resuspended in Opti-
153 MEM I medium containing 1% FBS, 2 mM MgCl₂, and 10 µM 5,7-dichlorokynurenic acid (DCKA,
154 HelloBio; in the case of NMDARs with mutant GluN2 subunit) or 10 µM D-2-amino-5-
155 phosphonopentanoic acid (D-APV, HelloBio; in the case of NMDARs with mutant GluN1 subunit),
156 to reduce cell death caused by excitotoxicity. For microscopy, HEK293 cells were grown in 12-
157 well plates and transfected with a total of 0.45 µg of DNA vectors carrying genes encoding GluN1
158 and GluN2 subunits at a ratio of 1:2 (YFP-/GFP-GluN subunit versus untagged GluN subunit),
159 using 1 µl of Lipofectamine 2000 reagent (Thermo Fischer Scientific) in 50 µl of Opti-MEM I
160 medium. DNA vectors carrying wild-type (WT) or mutant ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a constructs
161 were co-transfected at a 1:2 ratio with untagged GluN2A or GluN3A subunits.

162 All animal procedures were performed in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines and the
163 European Commission Council Directive 2010/63/EU for animal experiments. Primary cultures of
164 hippocampal neurons were prepared from Wistar rats of both sexes (at embryonic day 18) by

165 dissecting hippocampal neurons in a cold dissection solution consisting of Hanks' balanced salt
166 solution supplemented with 10 mM HEPES (pH 7.4). Hippocampi were then incubated in a
167 dissection medium containing 0.05% trypsin and 0.1 mg/ml DNase I (Merck) for 20 min at 37°C.
168 Dissociated cells were plated on poly-L-lysine-coated glass coverslips at a density of $2 \times 10,000$
169 cells per cm^2 in a plating medium consisting of minimal essential medium (MEM) supplemented
170 with 10% heat-inactivated horse serum, N2 supplement (1x), 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 20 mM D-
171 glucose, 25 mM HEPES, and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. After 3 hours, the plating medium was
172 replaced entirely with Neurobasal medium enriched with 2% B-27 and 2 mM L-glutamine (all
173 purchased from Thermo Fischer Scientific). Every 3-4 days, ~50% of the volume of this culture
174 medium was replaced with fresh medium. Hippocampal neurons were transfected at day 6 *in vitro*
175 (DIV6) with DNA vectors carrying genes encoding the indicated GluN subunits using
176 Lipofectamine 2000 (Lichnerova et al., 2015).

177

178 *Immunofluorescence microscopy*

179 Immunofluorescence labeling was performed 24 hours after the completion of transfection of
180 HEK293 cells. Hippocampal neurons were labeled 48 hours after the completion of transfection
181 (DIV14). All primary and secondary antibodies were diluted in a blocking solution consisting of
182 PBS and 0.2% (v/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA, Merck). Cells were first washed with ice-cold
183 PBS and incubated for 5 min in a blocking solution on ice. Surface antigens were labeled with
184 primary antibody (rabbit anti-GFP, 1:1000, Merck) for 15 min on ice, and then cells were washed
185 with ice-cold blocking solution and incubated with secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit with Alexa
186 Fluor 555, 1:1000, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Cells were then washed with ice-cold PBS, fixed in
187 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) in PBS for 15 min, permeabilized with 0.25% Triton X-100 in PBS
188 for 5 min, and incubated with primary antibody (mouse anti-GFP, 1:1000, Neuromab), and then
189 with secondary antibody (goat anti-mouse conjugated with Alexa Fluor 488, 1:1000, Thermo
190 Fisher Scientific) to label intracellular antigens.

191 To examine the internalization rate, surface-expressed NMDARs were labeled as
192 described above. After incubation with primary antibody, HEK293 cells were returned to a
193 conditioned medium without antibody and maintained in a cell culture incubator for 30 min.
194 Subsequently, the cells were washed with PBS, fixed in 4% PFA in PBS for 7 min, and blocked
195 with 0.2% BSA for 5 min. Cells were then incubated with a secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit
196 conjugated with Alexa Fluor 647, 1:250, Thermo Fisher Scientific). After permeabilization with
197 0.25% Triton X-100 in PBS, cells were incubated in a blocking solution supplemented with 0.1%
198 Triton for 30 minutes, followed by incubation with another secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit

199 conjugated with Alexa Fluor 555, 1:500, Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 30 minutes to label
200 internalized NMDARs.

201 In experiments with ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a constructs, HEK293 cells were first
202 incubated with ARIAD ligand at a concentration of 1 μ M (AL; D/D Solubilizer; Takara) for the
203 indicated times, fixed with PFA for 7 min, labeled using primary antibody (mouse anti-
204 mNEONGreen, 1:1000, ChromoTek) and secondary antibody (goat anti-mouse conjugated with
205 Alexa Fluor 555, 1:1000, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and re-fixed by PFA; intracellular
206 mNEONGreen epitopes in HEK293 cells were not labeled with antibodies. To detect the cis-GA
207 structures, we used fixed HEK293 cells labeled with primary antibody (rabbit anti-GM130, 1:1000,
208 Merck) and secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit conjugated with Alexa Fluor 555, 1:1000; labeled
209 cells were then re-fixed with PFA in PBS for 5 min. Microscopic samples were mounted on glass
210 slides using ProLong Antifade reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

211 Images were captured using either an Olympus FV10i microscope with a 60x/1.35 oil
212 immersion objective (relative surface expression, co-localization with GA) or an Olympus
213 SpinSR10 microscope with a 60x/1.42 oil immersion objective (internalization assay) and
214 analyzed using ImageJ 1.52N software (National Institutes of Health). In the case of HEK293
215 cells, total and surface (also the internalized) fluorescence intensity signals were analyzed on
216 whole cells; in the case of hippocampal neurons, 10 separate 5- μ m segments of secondary or
217 tertiary dendrites from a single neuron were analyzed. The degree of co-localization of GM130
218 and mNEONGreen signals was determined as the ratio between the intensity of the
219 mNEONGreen signal co-localizing with the GM130 signal and the intensity of the mNEONGreen
220 signal outside the co-localization region as used previously (Skrenkova et al., 2019). The following
221 competitive antagonists were employed for microscopical experiments: trans-2-Carboxy-5,7-
222 dichloro-4-phenylaminocarbonylamino-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline (L-689-560; Tocris); 7-Chloro-
223 4-hydroxy-3-(3-phenoxy)phenyl-2(1H)-quinolinone (L-701-324; Tocris); (R)-3-(2-
224 Carboxypiperazin-4-yl)propyl-1-phosphonic acid ((R)-CPP; Merck); [((1S)-1-(4-
225 Bromophenyl)ethyl)amino](1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,3-dioxo-5-quinoxaliny)methyl] phosphonic acid
226 tetrasodium salt (PEAQX; HelloBio).

227

228 *Electrophysiology*

229 Whole-cell current responses of HEK293 cells were recorded by the patch-clamp method ~24-48
230 hours after completion of transfection using an Axopatch 200B amplifier (Axon Instruments) with
231 series resistance (<10 M Ω) and capacitance compensation (~80%). Current responses of
232 NMDARs were recorded in voltage-clamp mode with constant membrane potential held at -60

233 mV, filtered using an eight-pole Bessel filter (frequency < 2 kHz), sampled at 5 kHz using Digidata
234 1550 (Molecular Devices), and recorded using pCLAMP 10.7 software (Axon Instruments).
235 Borosilicate glass micropipettes with a tip resistance of ~4-5 MΩ were prepared using a P-1000
236 puller (Sutter Instruments) and then filled with an intracellular recording solution containing (in
237 mM) 120 gluconic acid, 15 CsCl, 10 BAPTA, 10 HEPES, 3 MgCl₂, 1 CaCl₂, and 2 ATP-Mg salts
238 (pH 7.2 adjusted with CsOH). The standard extracellular recording solution (ECS) contained (in
239 mM) 160 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, 10 D-glucose, 0.2 EDTA, and 0.7 CaCl₂ (pH 7.3 adjusted
240 with NaOH). ECS containing the indicated concentrations of L-glutamate and glycine were applied
241 using a multi-barrel rapid application system with a time constant of solution exchange around
242 the recorded cell of ~20 ms (Skrenkova et al., 2020). All electrophysiological recordings were
243 acquired at room temperature. To demonstrate the functionality of GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-
244 R523A/GFP-GluN2A, GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y730A, and GluN1-4a/GFP-
245 GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y761A receptors, we used a 1-min treatment with 50 mM 2-
246 mercaptoethanol (BME; Merck) (Blanke and VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu, 2010).

247 The concentration-dependent effects of agonists were analyzed using *Equation (1)*:
248 $I = I_{\max} / (1 + (EC_{50}/[\text{agonist}])^h)$, where I_{\max} is the maximal steady-state current amplitude in
249 response to agonist, EC_{50} is the concentration of the agonist eliciting half of the maximal response,
250 $[\text{agonist}]$ is the concentration of agonist, and h is the apparent Hill coefficient. The approach for
251 estimation of K_d values is described in Text S1.

252

253 *Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511*
254 *residues*

255 Complex crystal structures of LBDs of human GluN1/GluN2A receptors were obtained from the
256 RSCB Protein Data Bank (PDB ID: 5KCJ) (Hackos et al., 2016). Prior to molecular modeling, the
257 positive allosteric modulator GNE-6901 was removed from the protein-ligand complex. A total of
258 18 LBD structures were prepared and simulated, including the WT GluN1 subunit along with eight
259 single-point mutants: GluN1-S688A, GluN1-S688P, GluN1-S688C, GluN1-S688N, GluN1-
260 S688E, GluN1-S688K, GluN1-S688W, and GluN1-S688Y. Similarly, the GluN2A subunit was
261 studied in its WT form alongside eight corresponding single-point mutations: GluN2A-S511A,
262 GluN2A-S511P, GluN2A-S511C, GluN2A-S511N, GluN2A-S511E, GluN2A-S511K, GluN2A-
263 S511W, and GluN2A-S511L. Homology models for all selected LBD structures were modeled on
264 a SWISS-MODEL server (Waterhouse et al., 2018) based on UNIPROT targeted sequences
265 (UNIPROT ID: Q05586 for GluN1 and UNIPROT ID: Q12879 for GluN2A). Protonation states of
266 all ionizable residues at physiological pH were assigned for individual LBD variants using the H++

267 method (Anandakrishnan et al., 2012). Standard AMBER parametrization procedure was used to
268 parametrize glycine and L-glutamate molecules with protonation corresponding to physiological
269 pH. Partial charges were calculated using the Gaussian 16 program (Gaussian 16, 2016) using
270 HF/6-31G* theory level in the gas phase. Parametrized ligands were aligned to precise crystal
271 positions based on the 5KCJ structure.

272 All molecular dynamics simulations were carried out using AMBER24 simulation software.
273 (Amber 2024, 2024) Amber ff19SB force field parameters were used for protein description (Tian
274 et al., 2020). All LBD variants were positioned within a cubic simulation box ($13 \times 13 \times 13$ nm)
275 and subsequently solvated using the OPC water model (Izadi et al., 2014). Li-Merz ions
276 (Sengupta et al., 2021) were added to replicate the physiological Na^+/Cl^- ion concentration of 150
277 mM and to ensure system electroneutrality. Prior to the main production run, each system was
278 subjected to energy minimization and gradual thermalization from 10 K to 303.15 K. The final
279 production runs of individual LBD variants were conducted in the NVT ensemble with a time step
280 of 2 fs and a total length of simulation time set to 1 μs . The weak-coupling algorithm (Berendsen
281 et al., 1984) maintained the temperature at 310.15 K with a temperature coupling constant of 0.2
282 ps. During MD simulation, all hydrogen-containing bonds were constrained using the SHAKE
283 algorithm (Ryckaert et al., 1977). A 1.0 nm cutoff was applied to the Lennard-Jones and short-
284 range electrostatic interactions, while long-range electrostatics were handled using Particle Mesh
285 Ewald (PME) summation (Darden et al., 1993). Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were applied
286 in all directions of a cubic simulation box. The key structural features of individual simulated
287 systems were analyzed using the *cptraj* tool (Roe and Cheatham, 2013). The root mean square
288 deviation (RMSD) was used to monitor the overall stability of the receptor by measuring deviations
289 of atomic positions with respect to the initial (crystal) structure. The root mean square fluctuation
290 (RMSF) was used to quantify the flexibility of individual residues with protein sequence to identify
291 regions with significant conformational changes. Furthermore, solvent-accessible surface area
292 (SASA) analysis assessed the extent of solvent exposure and provided insights into the overall
293 compactness of individual LBD variants. To evaluate the energy behind the binding interaction of
294 ligands (glycine or L-glutamate) within the LBDs of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits, molecular
295 mechanics Poisson–Boltzmann surface area (MM-PBSA) calculations (Miller et al., 2012) were
296 performed. All analyses were performed from the last 500 ns of the production simulations.

297 298 *Statistical analyses*

299 For microscopical data, statistical analysis was performed for normalized and log-transformed
300 data to stabilize variability against the mean. Data were cleaned of outliers outside the 1.5 times

301 interquartile range and tested for normality using the D'Agostino-Pearson test. Statistical
302 significance was tested using a one-factor or two-factor (experiments with ARIAD-mNEON-
303 GluN1-1a construct) ANOVA, followed by Tukey's variant of multiple comparisons via Matlab
304 (Matlab, 2022b; using the functions `anova1`, `anovan`, and `multcompare`). Negative controls in the
305 microscopy experiments document the quality of the microscopy staining performed but were not
306 included in the statistical analyses because only one GluN1 or GluN2 subunit was expressed.
307 Differences with a p-value <0.050 were considered statistically significant; data are presented as
308 mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The *robustfit* function in Matlab was used to analyze
309 the linear regression; points whose linear regression residuals were ≥ 2 times the median absolute
310 deviation (MAD) were identified as outliers. The regression quality was expressed as R^2
311 (coefficient of determination), and the 95% confidence intervals of the regression line were
312 calculated using the *predint* function (parameter `functional = on`). Pearson's coefficients of linear
313 correlation (expressed as r) and corresponding p-values were determined to validate the
314 statistical significance of the observed correlations using the *corr* function in Matlab. If the p-value
315 was >0.05 , we interpreted the correlation as non-significant. The strength of the correlation was
316 determined by the absolute value of r , classified as follows: very strong (0.80-1.00), strong (0.60-
317 0.79), moderate (0.40-0.59), weak (0.20-0.39) and very weak (0.01-0.19).

318

319 **Results**

320 *Alanine substitutions of amino acid residues in the LBD of the GluN1 subunit differentially alter*
321 *the surface delivery of GluN1/GluN2A receptors*

322 We aimed to determine whether the alanine substitution of amino acid residues in the LBD of the
323 GluN1 subunit that directly interacts with its agonist glycine alters the early trafficking of
324 GluN1/GluN2A receptors. Previous structural studies have shown that within the LBD of the
325 GluN1 subunit, the carboxyl group of glycine interacts with the guanidine group of residue R523,
326 the amino groups of residues T518 and S688, and the hydroxy group of residue S688. The amino
327 group of glycine interacts with residues P516, T518, and D732, the side chain of residue F484 is
328 responsible for the hydrophobic interaction with glycine, and the closed LBD structure is formed
329 by an interdomain interaction between residues Q405, W731, and D732 (Figure 1B) (Furukawa
330 and Gouaux, 2003; Inanobe et al., 2005). We first decided to co-express the WT YFP-GluN1-1a
331 or mutant YFP-GluN1-1a subunits together with the WT GluN2A subunit in HEK293 cells because
332 (i) the GluN1-1a splice variant is retained in the ER in the absence of GluN2 subunits (Huh and
333 Wenthold, 1999), (ii) the GluN2A subunit is abundantly represented GluN2 subtype in the adult
334 forebrain (Monyer et al., 1994; Sheng et al., 1994; Maier et al., 2007), (iii) the role of LBDs of both

335 the GluN1 or GluN2A subunits in the regulation of early trafficking of the GluN1/GluN2A receptor
336 has not been comprehensively tested, and (iv) HEK293 cells do not express endogenous GluN
337 subunits and are commonly used to study the trafficking and functional properties of the NMDARs
338 (Collett and Collingridge, 2004). To minimize the risk of excitotoxic damage caused by the
339 expression of NMDARs, we cultured transfected HEK293 cells in a medium supplemented with
340 1% FBS, 2 mM Mg²⁺, and 10 μM D-APV or 10 μM DCKA (as described in Methods). In addition,
341 we used HEK293 cells only up to 10 passages, and each experiment had negative (i.e., YFP-
342 GluN1-1a subunit) and positive (i.e., YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptor) controls. To accurately
343 detect differences between WT and mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors, we labeled surface
344 NMDARs by combining a primary polyclonal rabbit anti-GFP antibody with a secondary Alexa
345 555-labeled anti-rabbit antibody. Although this combination of primary and secondary antibodies
346 can cluster surface NMDARs, we do not foresee a bias in our microscopic data because this
347 approach (i) provided comparable results to using fluorescently labeled anti-GFP nanobodies in
348 our recent study (Kolcheva et al., 2023) but (ii) amplifies the surface signal of NMDARs compared
349 to anti-GFP nanobodies, allowing more accurate detection of differences in surface expression of
350 mutant NMDARs. Initially, we individually replaced the GluN1-Q405, GluN1-F484, GluN1-P516,
351 GluN1-T518, GluN1-R523, GluN1-S688, GluN1-W731, and GluN1-D732 residues, with alanine
352 residues (i.e., a neutral amino acid that should not dramatically alter protein structure) in the YFP-
353 GluN1-1a subunit. Using anti-GFP antibody immunostaining, we measured surface and total
354 expression levels of WT and mutant YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors; examples of images of
355 transfected HEK293 cells are shown in Figure 1C. We found that the surface expression of YFP-
356 GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors carrying alanine substitutions showed the following relationship:
357 WT> GluN1-S688A> GluN1-Q405A> GluN1-P516A> GluN1-T518A> GluN1-F484A> GluN1-
358 W731A> GluN1-D732A> GluN1-R523A (Figure 1D). We next performed whole-cell patch-clamp
359 recordings from HEK293 cells expressing WT and mutant YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors to
360 learn how alanine substitutions in LBD of the GluN1 subunit alter EC₅₀ values for glycine. We
361 elicited the current responses using ECS containing a range of appropriate glycine concentrations
362 (≤10 mM due to potential problems with higher osmolarity) with a fixed concentration of 300 μM
363 L-glutamate and maintaining the membrane potential at -60 mV (Figure 1E). Our
364 electrophysiological experiments showed that HEK293 cells expressing the YFP-GluN1-1a-
365 D732A/GluN2A receptor did not generate current responses at any of the glycine concentrations
366 tested, consistently with our microscopical data showing their disrupted surface expression (see
367 Figure 1D). HEK293 cells expressing the remaining mutant YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors
368 produced measurable current responses induced by L-glutamate and various glycine

369 concentrations, allowing us to generate concentration-response curves for glycine (Figure 1F).
370 The calculated EC₅₀ values for glycine at YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors carrying alanine
371 substitutions showed the following relationship: GluN1-Q405A< WT< GluN1-S688A< GluN1-
372 P516A< GluN1-T518A< GluN1-W731A< GluN1-F484A< GluN1-R523A (Table 1). The values of
373 relative surface expression exhibited a very strong and statistically significant negative correlation
374 with the EC₅₀ values for glycine ($r = -0.84$, $p = 0.009$), explaining 70% of the variability ($R^2 = 0.70$)
375 (Figure 1G). Thus, our experiments showed that alanine replacements in LBD of the GluN1
376 subunit mediate alterations in the surface expression of YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors which
377 are very strongly correlated with the EC₅₀ values for glycine.

378 The CTD splice variants of the GluN1 subunit show remarkable differences in their surface
379 expression. As described above, the GluN1-1a subunit requires the presence of the GluN2
380 subunit for its release from the ER; in contrast, the GluN1-4a subunit shows robust expression on
381 the cell surface even without the GluN2 subunit (Okabe et al., 1999). Next, we performed an
382 analogous microscopic and electrophysiological analysis in HEK293 cells transfected with WT or
383 untagged GluN1-4a subunits carrying the alanine replacements and the WT GFP-GluN2A subunit
384 as above with the YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors. We found the following relationship for the
385 relative surface expression of mutant GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors: WT> GluN1-S688A>
386 GluN1-Q405A> GluN1-P516A> GluN1-T518A> GluN1-F484A> GluN1-W731A> GluN1-D732A>
387 GluN1-R523A (Figure 1H). The values of relative surface expression were very strongly and
388 negatively correlated ($r = -0.80$, $p = 0.017$) with the obtained EC₅₀ values for glycine (Figure 1I,
389 Table 1), explaining 64% of the variability ($R^2 = 0.64$) (Figure 1J). In the case of HEK293 cells
390 transfected with GluN1-4a-D732A/GFP-GluN2A receptor, we detected only the current responses
391 <100 pA, preventing their detailed concentration-dependent analysis. The measured EC₅₀ values
392 for glycine did not differ between the corresponding mutant YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A and GluN1-
393 4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors, showing that the presence of GFP or YFP tags as well as differently
394 spliced CTDs of the GluN subunit, do not affect the EC₅₀ values for glycine (Figure 1F,I; Table 1).
395 Our experiments showed that specific alanine substitutions in the LBD of the GluN1 subunit
396 differentially alter the surface trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors, independent of the splice
397 variant of the GluN1 subunit.

398 *Alanine substitutions of amino acid residues in the LBD of the GluN2A subunit differentially alter*
399 *the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors*

400 We next sought to answer whether alanine substitutions of the amino acid residues involved in its
401 interaction with L-glutamate in LBD of the GluN2A subunit affect the surface expression of
402 GluN1/GluN2A receptors. Previous structural studies with LBD of the GluN2A subunit have shown

403 that the α -carboxyl group of L-glutamate interacts with the side group of residue R518 and with
404 the amino groups of residues S689 and T513 and that the amino group of L-glutamate interacts
405 with the hydroxy groups of residues S511 and T513 and, via the water molecule, with the γ -
406 carboxyl group of residue E413 and the hydroxy group of residue Y761. Also, the γ -carboxyl group
407 of L-glutamate interacts with the amino groups of residues S689 and T690 and the hydroxy group
408 of residue T690. In addition, L-glutamate in LBD is stabilized by hydrophobic interactions with
409 residues H485 and Y730, and the side chains of residues E413 and Y730 form inter-domain
410 interactions (Figure 2A) (Laube et al., 2004; Furukawa et al., 2005; Chen and Wyllie, 2006; Maier
411 et al., 2007; Jespersen et al., 2014). To reduce the number of the studied mutant NMDARs, the
412 GluN2A-V685, GluN2A-G688, and GluN2A-E691 residues involved in the interaction with L-
413 glutamate via two water molecules were not further tested (Jespersen et al., 2014). Furthermore,
414 the GluN2A-D731 residue was omitted due to conflicting findings in previous studies, which
415 presented varying perspectives on its interaction with L-glutamate, suggesting direct interaction
416 (Jespersen et al., 2014), interaction via water molecules (Hansen et al., 2021), and no interaction
417 with L-glutamate (Furukawa et al., 2005). We co-transfected HEK293 cells with WT or mutant
418 GFP-GluN2A subunits containing the E413A, H485A, S511A, T513A, R518A, S689A, T690A,
419 Y730A, and Y761A mutations, together with the WT GluN1-4a subunit; as this GluN subunit
420 combination allows more straightforward electrophysiological characterization of mutant
421 NMDARs with reduced surface expression (as shown in Figure 1). We immunofluorescently
422 labeled HEK293 cells expressing WT and mutant GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors using an anti-
423 GFP antibody (Figure 2B); our subsequent microscopical analysis showed the following trend in
424 their surface expression: GluN2A-S511A>WT> GluN2A-S689A>GluN2A-T690A> GluN2A-
425 H485A> GluN2A-T513A> GluN2A-R518A> GluN2A-E413A> GluN2A-Y730A> GluN2A-Y761A
426 (Figure 2C). Then, we elicited the current responses by application of L-glutamate in the
427 appropriate concentration range (10 mM) in the continuous presence of 100 μ M glycine (Figure
428 2D). The analysis of the concentration-response curves for L-glutamate at GluN1-4a/GFP-
429 GluN2A receptors showed the following trend for the EC_{50} values: WT< GluN2A-S689A< GluN2A-
430 S511A< GluN2A-T513A< GluN2A-E413A< GluN2A-Y730A<GluN2A-Y761A< GluN2A-H485A<
431 GluN2A-T690A< GluN2A-R518A (Figure 2E; Table 2). There was no correlation ($r = -0.62$, $p =$
432 0.075 , $R^2 = 0.38$) between the values of the relative surface expression and EC_{50} values for L-
433 glutamate (Figure 2F). The values obtained for the GluN1/GluN2A-S511A receptor were identified
434 as an outlier based on the statistical test described in the Materials and Methods section. These
435 results showed that alanine substitutions in the LBD of the GluN2A subunit regulate the surface
436 expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors independently of their EC_{50} values for L-glutamate.

437

438 *Synchronized release from the ER showed that alanine substitutions in LBDs alter the early*
439 *trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors*

440 We further used the ARIAD system, which allows the synchronized release of membrane
441 proteins from the ER by the addition of the ARIAD ligand (AL; Figure 3A) (Hangen et al., 2018) to
442 test the hypothesis that changes in surface expression of mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors are
443 caused at the level of early trafficking. We created ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a and ARIAD-
444 mNEON-GluN2A constructs and expressed them separately in HEK293 cells. Unfortunately,
445 HEK293 cells expressing the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN2A construct showed a distinct surface signal
446 detected by the anti-mNEONGreen antibody 24 hours after transfection, even without adding AL
447 (0 min, Figure S1). In contrast, HEK293 cells expressing the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct
448 showed no surface signal under control conditions (0 min) or 60 min after adding AL (Figure 3B).
449 Co-transfection of HEK293 cells with the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct and the WT
450 GluN2A subunit resulted in robust surface expression of the mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptor
451 60 min after addition of AL but not under control conditions (0 min), confirming the functionality of
452 the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct for studying early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors
453 (Figure 3C; time points 0, 30, 60 and 120 min after the addition of AL shown in Figure S2A and
454 for ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1/GluN3A receptor in Figure S2B). Given that only a smaller fraction of
455 functional GluN1/GluN2A receptors likely leave the ER structures in HEK293 cells (Huh and
456 Wenthold, 1999; Hawkins et al., 2004), their co-localization with GA is used as a measure to
457 quantify the early trafficking of NMDAR (She et al., 2012; Skrenkova et al., 2019). Therefore, we
458 co-transfected HEK293 cells with the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct, in combination with
459 the WT GluN2A subunit (or with the WT GluN3A subunit as a positive control) and labeled GA
460 structures on fixed cells with anti-GM130 antibody at 0 and 30 min after addition of AL (Figure
461 3D). Consistent with our previous experiments with GluN1/GFP-GluN3A receptors (Skrenkova et
462 al., 2019), our microscopical analysis showed that mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN3A receptor exhibited
463 a higher rate of co-localization with GA structures 30 min after addition of AL compared with
464 negative control (0 min). In contrast, mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors did not show a
465 different rate of co-localization with GA structures 30 min after the addition of AL compared with
466 negative control (0 min, Figure 3E); we obtained the same conclusion in another experiment
467 involving time points 0, 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes after the addition of AL (Figure S3). One
468 possible explanation is that GluN1/GluN2A receptors can bypass GA via an unconventional
469 pathway during early trafficking to the cell surface (see Discussion). Therefore, we did not analyze

470 the co-localization of mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors with GA structures to measure their early
471 trafficking, and we focused on characterizing their surface expression 60 min after adding AL.

472 To test whether mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors exhibit altered early trafficking, we
473 introduced four alanine substitutions into the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct, which caused
474 the most pronounced (~95% GluN1-R523A and ~90% GluN1-D732A) and moderate (~53%
475 GluN1-F484A and ~43% GluN1-P516A) reductions in surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A
476 receptors (Figure 1). Consistent with our previous results, GluN1-R523A and GluN1-D732A
477 mutations eliminated surface expression (~7% for GluN1-R523 and ~4% for GluN1-D732A). In
478 contrast, both GluN1-F484A and GluN1-P516A mutations caused ~42% resp. ~39% reduction in
479 surface expression of mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors measured 60 min after addition of AL
480 (Figure 3F). For further analysis using the ARIAD system, we selected, based on previous
481 experiments, four alanine substitutions in the LBD of the GluN2A subunit, two that caused the
482 most pronounced (~82% GluN2A-Y730A and ~87% GluN2A-Y761A) and two that showed
483 moderate (~38% GluN2A-T513A and ~59% GluN2A-R518A) reductions in surface expression of
484 GluN1/GluN2A receptors (Figure 2). Our analysis confirmed that the GluN2A-Y730A and GluN2A-
485 Y761A mutations were essentially eliminated (both ~12%) and that the GluN2A-T513A and
486 GluN2A-R518A mutations caused a ~41% resp. ~31% reduction in surface expression of
487 mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors in HEK293 cells at 60 min after addition of AL (Figure 3G).
488 Interestingly, the GluN1/GluN2A-S511A receptor exhibited increased levels of relative surface
489 expression compared to the WT GluN1/GluN2A receptor (Figure 2C). We next performed an
490 internalization assay with a primary anti-GFP antibody on the HEK239 cells transfected with the
491 WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-S511A receptors; representative
492 images are shown in Figure S4A. Consistent with our data described above, the GluN1-4a/GFP-
493 GluN2A-S511A receptor exhibited increased surface expression levels, but their relative
494 internalization rate was unaltered compared to WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptor (Figure
495 S4B). This indicates that the increased surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2A-S511A receptor
496 was not mediated by altered internalization rate. Therefore, we suggest that the observed
497 decrease in surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors with alanine substitutions in the LBDs
498 of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits is due to their altered early trafficking, likely during ER
499 processing.

500

501 *Alanine substitutions in the LBDs of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits independently affect the*
502 *surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors, regardless of the presence of the artificial*
503 *disulfide bonds that create the close conformations of the LBDs*

504 We then investigated whether alanine substitutions in LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits are
505 sensed independently by cellular control mechanisms. Therefore, we co-transfected HEK293
506 cells with a combination of WT and mutant GluN1-4a (containing F484A or P516A mutations) and
507 GFP-GluN2A (containing T513A or R518A mutations) subunits. Our analysis showed that in all
508 cases, the combination of two alanine substitutions (GluN1-4a-F484A/GFP-GluN2A-T513A,
509 GluN1-4a-F484A/GFP-GluN2A-R518A, GluN1-4a-P516A/GFP-GluN2A-T513A, and GluN1-4a-
510 P516A/GFP-GluN2A-R518A) caused reduced surface expression of the GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A
511 receptors (~90%) compared to the GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors containing only single
512 alanine substitutions (Figure 4A). Thus, our experiments showed that structural changes in the
513 LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits additively or synergistically regulate the early trafficking of
514 GluN1/GluN2A receptors and are likely recognized independently by control mechanisms.

515 Previous studies have found that the introduction of specific cysteine residues into LBDs
516 in the GluN1 (N499C-Q686C) and GluN2A (K487C-N687C) subunits leads to the closed cleft
517 conformation of the LBDs (Blanke and VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu, 2010; Dai and
518 Zhou, 2016). We first verified by electrophysiological measurements that GluN1-4a-N499C-
519 Q686C/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C receptor expressed in HEK293 cells generate current
520 responses elicited by ECS application in the absence of glycine and L-glutamate; also in the
521 presence of the competitive antagonists (10 μ M DCKA and 50 μ M D-APV; Figure 4B,C).
522 Subsequently, we found that HEK293 cells expressing GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A
523 receptor produced current responses in the presence of 1 mM L-glutamate only, which were
524 insensitive to 10 μ M DCKA (Figure 4D,E). In contrast, HEK293 cells expressing GluN1-4a/GFP-
525 GluN2A-K487C-N687C receptor had current responses elicited by 1 mM glycine only, which were
526 insensitive to 50 μ M D-APV (Figure 4F,G).

527 Subsequent microscopical experiments showed that GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-
528 GluN2A-K487C-N687C receptor exhibit profoundly reduced surface expression (~76%), the
529 GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A receptor showed a tendency in reduction (~27%), and
530 GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C receptor showed a decrease (~33%) in surface
531 expression compared to WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptor (Figure 4H). These data support
532 the conclusion that the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits additively or synergistically regulate
533 the early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. We next asked whether introducing alanine
534 substitutions in the LBDs of the GluN1 (R523A and D732A) or GluN2A (Y730A and Y761A)
535 subunits, which caused a profound reduction in surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors,
536 also affect surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors with closed cleft conformation of LBD.
537 Our microscopical analysis showed that single alanine substitutions in the closed cleft

538 conformation of LBDs of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits, i.e., in the case of GluN1-4a-N499C-
539 Q686C-R523A/GFP-GluN2A, GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-D732A/GFP-GluN2A, GluN1-4a/GFP-
540 GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y730A, and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y761A receptors
541 (Figure 4H), induced a profound decrease of their surface expression, comparable to the decline
542 observed for GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors carrying only the corresponding alanine
543 substitutions. Based on previous protocols (Blanke and VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu,
544 2010), we next aimed to verify the functionality and the formation of the artificial disulfide bonds
545 in the GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-R523A/GFP-GluN2A, GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-
546 Y730A, and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y761A receptors (GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-
547 D732A/GFP-GluN2A receptor was not examined as we observed only small current amplitudes
548 of the GluN1-D732A/GluN2A receptor expressed in the HEK293 cells). We induced the current
549 responses using 1 mM L-glutamate (GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-R523A/GFP-GluN2A) or 1 mM
550 glycine (GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y730A and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-
551 N687C-Y761A) and using both 1 mM L-glutamate and 1 mM glycine, which was followed by 1
552 min long application of 50 mM BME (Figure 4I). These experiments showed that all three tested
553 mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors produced detectable current responses induced by 1 mM L-
554 glutamate or 1 mM glycine, which were not altered by the co-application of both 1 mM L-glutamate
555 and 1 mM glycine, ruling out the possibility that the artificial disulfide bonds are formed in only a
556 small subset of surface GluN1/GluN2 receptors. In addition, the current responses were reduced
557 after pre-incubation with BME, which is in agreement with previous experiments at WT NMDARs
558 (Blanke and VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu, 2010). Notably, 50 mM BME tended to
559 reduce the current amplitudes more at the mutated (GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-R523A/GFP-
560 GluN2A, GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y730A, GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-
561 N687C-Y761A) than at the “non-mutated” (GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A, GluN1-
562 4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C) NMDARs containing artificial disulfide bonds, further supporting
563 the existence of artificial disulfide bonds in GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C-R523A/GFP-GluN2A,
564 GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-Y730A, and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-
565 Y761A receptors expressed on the cell surface of the HEK293 cells (Figure 4J). These
566 experiments demonstrated that the control mechanisms perceive alanine substitutions regardless
567 of the closed cleft conformation of LBDs of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits.

568 Finally, we investigated whether the presence of selected competitive antagonists affects
569 the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. Specifically, we used the commonly used
570 DCKA and two highly potent antagonists, L-689-560 and L-701-324, acting via the GluN1 subunit,
571 and the widely used D-APV and two highly potent antagonists, (R)-CPP and PEAQX, with high

572 selectivity for the GluN2A subunit (Traynelis et al., 2010). We cultured the HEK293 cells
573 expressing WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptor for 36 hours after the completion of the
574 transfection in the presence of 300 μ M of competitive antagonists, as higher concentrations could
575 mediate toxic effects on HEK293 cells (data not shown). We did not observe any differences in
576 the surface expression level of the WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A receptor in the presence of
577 competitive antagonists (Figure 4K). Using a chemical database (available at URL:
578 <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), we found the following predicted logP (octanol-water ratio;
579 XLogP3-AA) values: DCKA (2.5); L-689-560 (3.5); L-701-324 (4.5); D-APV (-5.3); (R)-CPP (-6.8);
580 PEAQX (-1.6). The examined competitive antagonists acting at the GluN1 subunit (DCKA, L-689-
581 560, and L-701-324) thus exhibit the optimal range of membrane permeability (>1) (Soliman et
582 al., 2021). Conversely, all the used competitive antagonists acting at the GluN2A subunit (D-APV,
583 (R)-CPP, and PEAQX) are hydrophilic and likely did not reach the ER in our experiments. Thus,
584 our data suggest that quality control mechanisms in the ER are not affected by the presence of
585 competitive antagonists acting at least at the GluN1 subunit. Future experiments are needed to
586 assess the precise concentrations of competitive antagonists in the ER. Nevertheless, our
587 experiments showed that long-term incubation with a panel of competitive antagonists did not
588 alter the surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2A receptor; this supports the use of competitive
589 antagonists in cell-based experiments to reduce NMDAR-induced excitotoxicity.

590
591 *The effect of selected alanine substitutions in LBDs on surface expression is conserved for*
592 *GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors*

593 We next asked whether the selected alanine substitutions in LBD of the GluN1 subunit, GluN1-
594 F484A, GluN1-P516A, GluN1-R523A, GluN1-S688A and GluN1-D732A, examined in more detail
595 in combination with the GluN2A subunit, alter similarly the surface expression of the
596 GluN1/GluN2B receptor. Using immunostaining with an anti-GFP antibody, we observed that the
597 relative surface expression levels of the YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2B receptors showed a similar order
598 to that of the YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors, specifically WT > GluN1-S688A > GluN1-F484A
599 > GluN1-P516A > GluN1-D732A > GluN1-R523A (Figure 5A). After plotting the surface
600 expression values with linear regression, we obtained a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.95$,
601 $p = 0.003$, $R^2 = 0.91$) between WT and mutant YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2A and YFP-GluN1-
602 1a/GluN2B receptors, indicating that the surface expression of both subtypes is similarly regulated
603 by alanine substitutions in LBD of the GluN1 subunit (Figure 5B).

604 We further investigated whether the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2B receptors is
605 regulated by alanine substitutions in the LBD of the GluN2B subunit, similar to the case of

606 GluN1/GluN2A receptors. The structure of the LBD of the GluN2B subunit with labeled amino acid
607 residues directly interacting with L-glutamate is shown in Figure 5C; interestingly, the amino acid
608 residues interacting with L-glutamate are conserved in all GluN2 subunits (Kinarsky et al., 2005).
609 Therefore, we further compared the surface expression of the GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2B receptors
610 containing the corresponding alanine substitutions, GluN2B-S512A, GluN2B-T514A, GluN2B-
611 R519A, GluN2B-Y731A, and GluN2B-Y761A, which we studied in detail in the case of
612 GluN1/GluN2A receptors. Analysis of the surface fluorescence signals of the GluN1-4a/GFP-
613 GluN2B receptors expressed in the HEK293 cells showed the following order: WT> GluN2B-
614 S512A> GluN2B-T514A> GluN2B-R519A> GluN2B-Y762A> GluN2B-Y731A (Figure 5D); which,
615 except for mutations causing highly deficient surface expression (GluN2B-R519A, GluN2B-
616 Y761A, GluN2B-Y731A), corresponded to the order obtained for homologous mutations in the
617 case of the GluN2A subunit (see Figure 2). This conclusion was confirmed by the very strong
618 positive correlation ($r = 0.93$, $p = 0.007$, $R^2 = 0.87$) between the relative surface expression of the
619 GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors containing the corresponding alanine substitutions
620 within the LBDs of the GluN2A and GluN2B subunits, respectively (Figure 5E). Our subsequent
621 electrophysiological recordings and concentration-dependent analysis of WT and mutant GluN1-
622 4a/GFP-GluN2B receptors revealed a very strongly positive correlation ($r = 0.95$, $p = 0.004$, $R^2 =$
623 0.90) between the EC_{50} values for L-glutamate measured for the GluN1/GluN2A and
624 GluN1/GluN2B receptors (Figure 5F, Figure S5, Table 3), showing that homologous alanine
625 substitutions in LBDs of the GluN2A and GluN2B subunits have similar effects on the sensitivity
626 of the mutated GluN1/GluN2 receptors to L-glutamate.

627
628 *Pathogenic variants of the specific amino acid residues in LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits*
629 *indicate tight regulation of the surface delivery of GluN1/GluN2A receptors*

630 We have searched the "GRIN variants DATABASE" (available at URL:
631 <https://alf06.uab.es/grindb/home>) for pathogenic and potentially pathogenic "missense" variants
632 (hereafter referred to as "pathogenic variants") of amino acid residues in LBDs involved in the
633 direct interaction of glycine with the GluN1 subunit and L-glutamate with the GluN2A subunit; their
634 list as of January 1, 2022, including relevant information, is provided in Table 4. To examine the
635 effect of the pathogenic variants on the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors, we chose
636 to combine YFP-hGluN1-1a and hGluN2A subunits, given that we do not have a functional tagged
637 version of the hGluN2A subunit. We labeled the HEK293 cells transfected with WT or mutated
638 YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors using an anti-GFP antibody (Figure 6A); analysis of
639 microscopical data revealed the following trends of surface expression levels for GluN1 subunit:

640 GluN1-S688Y> WT> GluN1-D732E> GluN1-S688P> GluN1-R523C (Figure 6B), and for GluN2A
641 subunit: WT> GluN2A-T513I> GluN2A-T690M> GluN2A-S511L> GluN2A-R518L> GluN2A-
642 R518C> GluN2A-R518H (Figure 6C). We then performed the same electrophysiological approach
643 described above using the HEK293 cells expressing WT and mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A
644 receptors, and we analyzed concentration-response curves for glycine (for pathogenic variants in
645 the GluN1 subunit) and L-glutamate (for pathogenic variants in the GluN2A subunit) (Figure 6D).
646 Concerning the pathogenic variants in the GluN1 subunit, we did not detect any current responses
647 in HEK293 cells transfected with the YFP-hGluN1-1a-R523C/hGluN2A receptor. In contrast, we
648 observed a profound 3,188-fold increase in EC_{50} values for glycine with YFP-hGluN1-1a-
649 S688P/hGluN2A, a 944-fold increase for YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688Y/hGluN2A, and a 1,457-fold
650 increase for YFP-hGluN1-1a-D732E/hGluN2A receptors (Figure 6E). Concerning the pathogenic
651 variants in the GluN2A subunit, we did not detect any current responses of YFP-hGluN1-
652 1a/hGluN2A-S511L, YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-R518H, YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-R518L, and
653 YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-T690M receptors even in the presence of 10 mM L-glutamate. In the
654 case of the YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-T513I and YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-R518C receptors, we
655 observed current responses only in the presence of 3 and 10 mM L-glutamate, and we did not
656 proceed with the concentration-response analysis. These experiments showed that pathogenic
657 variants in LBDs can have a prominent impact, distinct from the corresponding alanine
658 substitutions, on regulating the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors.

659
660 *The mutant cycles of the specific amino acid residues in LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits*
661 *indicate tight regulation of the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A receptors*

662 Interestingly, the surface expression levels determined for YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors
663 containing pathogenic variants were profoundly different compared to the corresponding alanine
664 substitutions for GluN1-S688 (~76% for the GluN1-S688A mutation compared to ~126% for the
665 hGluN1-S688Y or ~38% for the hGluN1-S688P variants; ~10% for the GluN1-D732A mutation
666 versus ~89% for the hGluN1-D732E variant; ~139% for the GluN2A-S511A mutation versus
667 ~25% for the hGluN2A-S511L variant; ~81% for the GluN2A-T690A mutation versus ~41% for
668 the hGluN2A-T690M variant). Considering the practical scope of subsequent experimental and *in*
669 *silico* analyses, we designed a series of mutant cycles targeting the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-
670 S511 residues. Specifically, we introduced substitutions in the YFP-hGluN1-1a and hGluN2A
671 subunits for alanine (A; small uncharged), cysteine (C; nucleophilic), proline (P; hydrophobic),
672 tryptophan (W; aromatic), glutamic acid (E; acidic), asparagine (N; amide), and lysine (K; basic).
673 Regarding the mutant cycle of the GluN1-S688 residue, our microscopical analysis showed the

674 following trend for the surface expression levels of YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors
675 expressed in HEK293 cells: WT>GluN1-S688N> GluN1-S688A> GluN1-S688E> GluN1-S688C>
676 GluN1-S688W> GluN1-S688P>GluN1-S688K (Figure 7A). Our electrophysiological
677 measurements showed that all YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing the mutant GluN1-
678 S688 residue cycle produced sufficient amplitudes of the current responses to obtain the EC_{50}
679 values for glycine (Figure 7B; Table 5). Subsequent analysis revealed a moderate negative
680 correlation ($r = -0.76$), explaining 76 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.57$) between the surface expression
681 levels and EC_{50} values for glycine at WT and mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors
682 containing the GluN1-S688 residue mutant cycle; this correlation was statistically significant ($p =$
683 0.048 ; Figure 7C). To corroborate our measured EC_{50} values for glycine, we estimated the K_d
684 values for glycine at WT and mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors by assessing τ_{on} and τ_{off}
685 values from the current responses elicited by different concentrations of glycine in the presence
686 of $100 \mu\text{M}$ L-glutamate (Figure S6; Text S1). Correlation analysis of the EC_{50} and K_d values for
687 WT and mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing the GluN1-S688 residue mutant
688 cycle showed a very strong correlation ($r = 1.00$), with a p-value of 0.00 and $R^2 = 1.00$ (Figure S7;
689 the fitting parameters in Table S1).

690 Regarding the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue, we observed the following trend
691 in the surface expression of YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors in HEK293 cells: GluN2A-
692 S511A>WT> GluN2A-S511N> GluN2A-S511C> GluN2A-S511P> GluN2A-S511E> GluN2A-
693 S511K> GluN2A-S511W (Figure 7D). Our electrophysiological measurements from HEK293 cells
694 expressing YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing GluN2A-S511N, GluN2A-S511K,
695 GluN2A-S511W mutations showed no current responses; therefore, we calculated EC_{50} values
696 for L-glutamate for the remaining mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors (Figure 7E; Table
697 5). Using linear regression, we did not observe a correlation ($r = -0.28$, $p = 0.647$, $R^2 = 0.08$)
698 between the relative surface expression levels and the EC_{50} values for L-glutamate for the YFP-
699 hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors with the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue (Figure 7F).
700 Correlation analysis of the EC_{50} and K_d values for WT and mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A
701 receptors containing the GluN1-S511 residue mutant cycle showed a very strong correlation ($r =$
702 1.00), with a p-value of 0.00 and $R^2 = 1.00$ (the representative current responses shown in Figure
703 S8; the correlation analysis in Figure S9; the fitting parameters in Table S1), corroborating our
704 measurements of the EC_{50} values for L-glutamate.

705 To explore the impact of the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511 residues
706 on the structural stability of LBDs and their propensity to change the ligand-binding sites locally,
707 we systematically modeled and simulated the individual mutations into the LBDs of GluN1 and

708 GluN2A subunits. The global stability of LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits, in both WT and
709 mutated forms, was evaluated using a comprehensive set of structural analyses, including the
710 RMSD of protein backbone residues (Figure 8A,G), the RMSF of individual residues (Figure S10
711 and S11), and the solvent-accessible surface area (SASA; Figure 8B, H), derived from 1 μ s-long
712 atomistic simulations. The RMSD value for the WT LBD of the GluN1 subunit was 2.31 ± 0.01 Å,
713 indicating a stable structure closely aligned with the crystal form. The RMSD values for the LBDs
714 of the mutated GluN1 subunit exhibited relatively large differences among WT and mutated LBDs
715 of the GluN1 subunit (Figure 8A). Our analysis revealed a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.75$),
716 explaining 75 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.56$) between the relative surface expression levels and
717 RMSD values for the WT and the GluN1-S688 residue mutant cycle; this correlation was
718 statistically significant ($p = 0.02$; Figure 8C). The LBD structures containing the two most extreme
719 mutations, GluN1-S688P and GluN1-S688K, showed RMSD values of 6.79 ± 0.11 Å and $9.55 \pm$
720 0.10 Å, respectively, indicating substantial deviations from the crystal structure. In addition, these
721 mutations led to the adoption of more extended LBD conformations that effectively opened the
722 glycine access/egress pathway, contrasting with the more compact conformation observed in the
723 crystal structure (Table 6). Next, our calculations revealed the SASA value of $14,217.90 \pm 14.26$
724 Å² for WT LBD of the GluN1 subunit; the subsequent analysis showed a moderately strong
725 negative correlation ($r = -0.69$), explaining 69 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.47$) between the relative
726 surface expression levels and SASA values for the WT and the GluN1-S688 residue mutant cycle;
727 this correlation was statistically significant ($p = 0.04$; Figure 8D). Consistently with our findings
728 described above, we revealed an increase in SASA values to $15,330.34 \pm 16.80$ Å² and $15,723.66$
729 ± 17.28 Å² for GluN1-S688P and GluN1-S688K mutations, respectively, supporting the hypothesis
730 that both mutations transition the LBD to more extended conformation, underscoring the shift
731 towards a less compact and more solvent-exposed structure. Furthermore, the LBDs containing
732 GluN1-S688P and GluN1-S688K mutations exhibited profound RMSF deviations compared to the
733 WT LBD, and the global structural alterations in the LBDs induced by GluN1-S688P and GluN1-
734 S688K mutations led to the dissociation of glycine from the ligand-binding site (Table 6). Finally,
735 by conducting MM-PBSA calculations, we obtained an $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ value of -32.18 ± 1.35 kcal/mol
736 for the WT LBD of the GluN1 subunit, consistent with the previous calculation (Chen et al., 2023).
737 The calculated $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for the WT and mutant LBDs of the GluN1 subunit containing the
738 GluN1-S688 residue mutant cycle exhibited a very strong negative correlation ($r = -0.93$),
739 explaining 93 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.87$) when compared with the experimentally measured
740 EC_{50} values for glycine; this correlation was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$; Figure 8E). In
741 addition, we observed a strong correlation ($r = 0.74$), explaining 74 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.54$)

742 between the relative surface expression and the $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for glycine for the GluN1-S688
743 residue mutant cycle; this correlation was statistically significant ($p = 0.023$; Figure 8F).
744 Consistently with the above-described findings, we observed $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values of -7.21 ± 3.77
745 kcal/mol and -1.84 ± 2.35 kcal/mol for the LBDs containing the GluN1-S688P and GluN1-S688K
746 mutations, respectively, indicating that both mutations profoundly destabilize the glycine-binding
747 site (Table 6).

748 The crystal structure was largely conserved for the WT LBD of the GluN2A subunit, as
749 indicated by an overall RMSD value of 2.28 ± 0.01 Å. The RMSD values for the GluN2A-S511
750 residue mutant cycle did not exceed 4.2 Å, with the highest deviation observed for the GluN2A-
751 S511K mutation (Table 6). This indicates that the overall fold of LBDs of the GluN2A subunit
752 remained stable despite the GluN2A-S511 residue mutations. Our analysis revealed no
753 correlation ($r = -0.33$, $R^2 = 0.11$, $p = 0.42$) between the relative surface expression levels and
754 RMSD values for the WT and mutant LBDs containing the GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle
755 (Figure 8I; Table 6). The SASA values for the LBDs containing the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-
756 S511 residue also remained relatively consistent, supporting the notion of a preserved structural
757 integrity of the LBD of the GluN2A subunit containing different mutations. Our analysis showed
758 no correlation ($r = -0.13$, $R^2 = 0.02$, $p = 0.74$) between the relative surface expression levels and
759 SASA values for the WT and mutant LBDs containing the GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle
760 (Figure 8J). Furthermore, the LBDs of the GluN2A subunit containing the GluN2A-S511 residue
761 mutant cycle exhibited only slight RMSF deviations compared to the WT LBD (Figure S11).
762 Finally, we calculated the $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ value of -36.50 ± 2.95 kcal/mol for L-glutamate binding into the
763 WT LBDs of the GluN2A subunit and the GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle. We also observed
764 relatively strong L-glutamate interaction with the LBDs containing the GluN2A-S511P ($-43.01 \pm$
765 1.81 kcal/mol), GluN2A-S511A (-34.81 ± 2.15 kcal/mol), and GluN2A-S511L (31.31 ± 2.00
766 kcal/mol) mutations. The least favorable L-glutamate binding was observed for the S511E
767 mutation (-25.37 ± 3.64 kcal/mol); likely, the negative charge introduced by the S511E mutation
768 destabilized the interaction with the negatively charged L-glutamate. Interestingly, we observed
769 no dissociation of L-glutamate for the above-tested mutated LBDs of the GluN2A subunit. In the
770 case of S511W, S511C, S511N, and S511K mutations, spontaneous dissociation of L-glutamate
771 was observed, resulting in distinctly lower $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values of -17.42 ± 5.21 kcal/mol, -11.76 ± 5.14
772 kcal/mol, -4.75 ± 3.75 kcal/mol and -3.85 ± 3.13 kcal/mol, respectively (Table 6). Unexpectedly,
773 in none of these cases where the L-glutamate spontaneously dissociated from the LBD, we did
774 not observe any structural changes underlying this process. This indicates that the less compact
775 structure of the LBD of the GluN2A subunit enables the L-glutamate to bind and unbind more

776 readily than we observed during simulations of glycine interaction with the LBD of the GluN1
777 subunit. The calculated $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for the WT and mutant LBDs of the GluN2A subunit
778 containing the GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle exhibited no correlation ($r = -0.73$, $p = 0.16$, R^2
779 $= 0.53$) compared with the measured EC_{50} values for L-glutamate (Figure 8K). The lack of
780 correlation between calculated $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ and the experimentally measured EC_{50} values for L-
781 glutamate could be explained by the more open conformation of the LBD of the GluN2A subunit
782 with exposed ligand-binding site; this structural characteristic allows spontaneous ligand
783 dissociation without global structural reengagements. We also cannot exclude the effect of the
784 cooperativity of the LBDs in the NMDAR heterotetramer, which may lead to no correlation
785 between EC_{50} and $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values. In addition, we observed no correlation ($r = 0.36$, $R^2 = 0.13$, p
786 $= 0.35$) between the relative surface expression and the $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for L-glutamate for the
787 GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle (Figure 8L). These analyses revealed distinct behaviors
788 between LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits and highlighted profound structural differences
789 among individual systems of the LBDs containing the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511 residue
790 mutant cycles.

791 In the next phase, we carried out a detailed investigation into the role of specific mutations
792 in the early trafficking of NMDARs, focusing on pathogenic variants including GluN1-S688Y
793 (which did not affect relative surface expression), GluN1-S688P (which decreased relative surface
794 expression by ~62%; both mutations shown in Figure 6), and GluN2A-S511L (which reduced
795 relative surface expression to ~25%), along with two additional mutations, GluN2A-S511A (the
796 only mutation that increased relative surface expression) and GluN2A-S511P (which reduced
797 relative surface expression by ~48%; all mutations shown in Figure 2 and 6). First, we created
798 the WT ARIAD-hGluN1-1a construct and introduced the hGluN1-S688Y and hGluN1-S688P
799 variants. Co-transfection of HEK293 cells with the WT ARIAD-hGluN1-1a construct and the WT
800 hGluN2A subunit resulted in robust surface expression of the WT mNEON-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A
801 receptor 60 min after addition of AL but not under control conditions (0 min) (Figure 9A-B). In line
802 with our data above, the hGluN1-S688Y variant did not affect the relative surface expression of
803 mNEON-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptor measured 60 min after AL addition, while the GluN1-
804 S688P variant reduced the relative surface expression by ~41% (Figure 9A-B). Additionally, co-
805 expressing the WT ARIAD-hGluN1-1a construct with mutated hGluN2A subunits led to either an
806 increase (~50% for the hGluN2A-S511A mutation) or a decrease (~31% for hGluN2A-S511P and
807 ~87% for hGluN2A-S511L variants) of the relative surface expression of mNEON-hGluN1-
808 1a/hGluN2A receptors 60 min after AL addition (Figure 9C). Under control conditions (0 min),
809 essentially no mNEON-hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors were detected on the cell surface (Figure 9C).

810 Thus, our data suggest that the observed changes in surface expression of hGluN1/hGluN2A
811 receptors with the studied mutations, including pathogenic variants in the LBDs, are caused by
812 altered early trafficking in the HEK293 cells.

813 We then investigated whether the presence of the pathogenic variants and other selected
814 mutations in the LBDs of hGluN1 and hGluN2A subunits is sensed independently by control
815 mechanisms. We co-transfected HEK293 cells with a combination of WT and mutant YFP-
816 hGluN1-1a (containing the S688P variant; the S688Y variant was not assessed as it does not
817 alter the surface delivery of the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors) and hGluN2A (containing hGluN2A-
818 S511A, hGluN2A-S511P and hGluN2A-S511L mutations) subunits. Our analysis revealed that in
819 all cases, the combination of two mutated hGluN subunits altered the surface expression of YFP-
820 hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors compared to YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing only
821 a single mutated hGluN1 or hGluN2A subunit (Figure 8D-F). Specifically, YFP-hGluN1-1a-
822 S688P/hGluN2A-S511A receptor exhibited no difference in relative surface expression compared
823 to WT YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptor, differing from the relative surface expression of both
824 YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A and YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511A receptors (Figure 9D).
825 YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A-S511P receptor exhibited a ~47% reduction compared to WT
826 YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptor, distinct from the values for YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A
827 and YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511P receptors (Figure 9E). Finally, YFP-hGluN1-1a-
828 S688P/hGluN2A-S511L receptor showed a ~97% reduction in surface expression compared to
829 WT YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptor, also differing from YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A and
830 YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511L receptors (Figure 9F). These findings indicate that pathogenic
831 variants and other selected mutations in the LBDs of hGluN1 and hGluN2A subunits additively or
832 synergistically regulate the surface expression of YFP-hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors.

833 We next investigated whether the presence of pathogenic variants and other mutants in
834 the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits also affect the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A
835 receptors containing closed cleft conformations induced by artificial disulfide bonds. We used rat
836 GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C and GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C constructs, which were functionally
837 validated by electrophysiology in Figure 4. Similar to the relative surface expression patterns
838 observed with YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors carrying mutations in the LBDs, the GluN1-
839 4a-N499C-Q686C-S688Y/GFP-GluN2A receptor showed no change, while the GluN1-4a-N499C-
840 Q686C-S688P/GFP-GluN2A receptor exhibited a ~35% reduction in relative surface expression
841 compared to the GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A receptor (Figure 9G). Additionally, the
842 GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-S511A receptor showed a ~79% increase, whereas the
843 GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-S511P receptor exhibited a ~16% decrease, and the

844 GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C-S511L receptor showed a ~73% reduction in relative
845 surface expression compared to the GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C receptor (Figure 9H).
846 These findings suggest that cellular mechanisms detect the presence of various mutations in the
847 LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits containing artificial disulfide bonds.

848 Finally, we asked whether our findings on the roles that specific mutations in LBDs play in
849 regulating the surface number of NMDARs expressed in HEK293 cells also apply to hippocampal
850 neurons. We first determined the surface expression of YFP-hGluN1-1a subunits carrying alanine
851 substitution and pathogenic variants of the hGluN1-S688 residue in cultured hippocampal
852 neurons (DIV 14) using an anti-GFP antibody (Figure 10A). Our microscopic analysis showed the
853 following decrease in relative surface expression of mutant YFP-hGluN1-1a subunits compared
854 to the WT YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit: YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688A (~48% compared to ~23% in HEK293
855 cells; Figure 10B), and YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P (~76% compared to ~59% in HEK293 cells; Figure
856 10B); the YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688Y subunit did not exhibit altered relative surface expression in
857 hippocampal neurons (Figure 10B). We could not directly verify the surface expression of the
858 mutant hGluN2A subunits in hippocampal neurons because we did not have a functional tagged
859 hGluN2A subunit. Therefore, we next transfected the WT YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit or co-
860 transfected WT YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit with the WT hGluN2A subunit. Our microscopic analysis
861 showed that the presence of the hGluN2A subunit profoundly increased the surface expression
862 of the WT YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit (Figure 10C). This is consistent with the previous finding that
863 mammalian neurons produce an excess of GluN1 subunit but a limited number of GluN2 subunits
864 (Prybylowski et al., 2002); this supports the validity of the surface expression assay with the WT
865 YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit and untagged mutant hGluN2A subunits. Our subsequent analysis of the
866 hippocampal neurons showed that the presence of the hGluN2A-S511A subunit led to a ~39%
867 increase, while co-expression with the hGluN2A-S511P and hGluN2A-S511L subunits resulted in
868 a decrease of ~21% and ~68%, respectively, of the relative surface expression of the WT YFP-
869 hGluN1-1a subunit compared with the WT hGluN2A subunit (Figure 10D). These findings support
870 the relevance of our conclusions about regulating the surface numbers of the NMDARs obtained
871 using HEK293 cells.

872

873 Discussion

874 Previous studies of early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2 receptors studied a limited number of alanine
875 substitutions that directly interact with glycine in the GluN1 subunit or L-glutamate in the GluN2A
876 subunit. Specifically, the GluN1-D732A/GluN2A receptor showed a ~90% reduction in surface
877 expression, which was associated with a ~35,000-fold increase in the EC₅₀ value for glycine

878 measured for the GluN1-D732A/GluN2B receptor expressed in *Xenopus* oocytes (Williams et al.,
879 1996; Kenny et al., 2009). Our experiments with the GluN1-D732A/GluN2A receptor also showed
880 a ~90% reduction in surface expression, although we did not detect any current responses from
881 transfected HEK293 cells. Previously, the GluN1/GluN2B-E413A receptor showed a ~80%
882 reduction in surface expression (She et al., 2012) and a ~237-fold increase in EC₅₀ value for L-
883 glutamate (Laube et al., 2004). Consistent with this, our data with the GluN1/GluN2A-E413A
884 receptor showed a ~80% reduction in surface expression and a ~287-fold increase in EC₅₀ value
885 for L-glutamate. In addition, EC₅₀ values were also previously calculated for the following mutants
886 of GluN1/GluN2A receptors: GluN1-F484A/GluN2A (glycine: 3,100 μM versus our measured
887 value of 3,624 μM) (Kvist et al., 2013), GluN1-R523A/GluN2A (glycine: 5,400 μM versus our
888 measured value of 10,261 μM) (Kvist et al., 2013), GluN1/GluN2A-S511A (L-glutamate: 146 μM
889 versus our measurement of 235 μM) (Chen et al., 2005), GluN1/GluN2A-H485A (L-glutamate:
890 490-1,025 μM versus our measurement of 3,969 μM) (Anson et al., 1998; Chen et al., 2005; Maier
891 et al., 2007), GluN1/GluN2A-T513A (L-glutamate: 482 μM versus our measurement of 809 μM)
892 (Chen et al., 2005), GluN1/GluN2A-R518A (L-glutamate: >3000 μM versus our measurement of
893 8,895 μM) (Erreger et al., 2007), GluN1/GluN2A-S689A (L-glutamate: ~2-5 μM versus our
894 measurement of 7 μM) (Anson et al., 1998; Erreger et al., 2007) and GluN1/GluN2A-T690A (L-
895 glutamate: 2,967 μM versus our measurement of 5,254 μM) (Anson et al., 1998). The observed
896 differences in EC₅₀ values can be explained by the use of different expression systems (*Xenopus*
897 oocytes versus HEK293 cells), electrophysiological methods (two-electrode voltage clamp versus
898 whole-cell patch-clamp), and differences in the composition of the recording solutions. Our series
899 of alanine substitutions showed a statistically significant (mutant GluN1 subunit) and no (mutant
900 GluN2A subunit) correlation between surface expression levels of GluN1/GluN2A receptors and
901 their EC₅₀ values. Thus, our data showed that replacing critical amino acid residues within the
902 LBDs of the GluN1 subunit with a small uncharged alanine does not, at least in the case of the
903 GluN2A subunit, support the previously hypothesized link between surface expression levels and
904 the agonist potency of GluN1/GluN2 receptors. In addition, we found that co-expression of both
905 GluN1 and GluN2A subunits with alanine substitutions in LBDs exhibited an additive or synergistic
906 effect on reducing the surface expression level of GluN1/GluN2A receptors, leading to the
907 conclusion that LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2 subunits contribute independently to the regulation of
908 the surface numbers of NMDARs. Our experiments with the closed cleft conformation of LBDs
909 (Blanke and VanDongen, 2008; Kussius and Popescu, 2010; Dai and Zhou, 2016) confirmed the
910 additive or synergistic effect of the LBDs of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits on the regulation of
911 the surface numbers of the GluN1/GluN2A receptors. Our subsequent experiments revealed that

912 closed cleft conformation of the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits did not mask the reducing
913 effect of alanine and other substitutions on the surface numbers of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. We
914 further showed that incubating the transfected HEK293 cells with a panel of competitive
915 antagonists did not alter the surface numbers of WT GluN1/GluN2A receptors. This result is
916 consistent with previous data on the effect of DCKA on the early trafficking of WT GluN1/GluN2A
917 receptor (Kenny et al., 2009). Our experiments with alanine substitutions in the LBDs of
918 GluN1/GluN2B receptors revealed similar findings to those observed with GluN1/GluN2A
919 receptors, which suggests an evolutionarily shared mechanism for the regulation of the early
920 trafficking of these two major diheteromeric subtypes of NMDARs.

921 Using the synchronized release of NMDARs from the ER, we showed that GluN1/GluN3A
922 receptor co-localized with GA structures, similar to GluA1 receptor (Hangen et al., 2018).
923 Consistently with a previous study showing diffuse localization of GluN1/GluN2A receptor in
924 HEK293 cells (Hayashi et al., 2009), we did not detect GluN1/GluN2A receptors in GA, even at
925 15, 30, 45, and 60 min after addition of AL. Thus, the GluN1/GluN2A receptor may bypass the
926 GA, as shown in a previous study with a transfected GluN1 subunit (Jeyifous et al., 2009). It was
927 previously demonstrated that the WT GluN1/GluN2B receptor co-localizes with GA in COS-7 cells
928 (She et al., 2012). Our pilot experiment did not detect WT GluN1/GluN2B receptors in GA
929 structures using the ARIAD system; this discrepancy may be explained by the fact that expression
930 of recombinant GluN1/GluN2B receptors may cause defragmentation of GA structures (Nakagomi
931 et al., 2008) or cause excitotoxic damage (Zhou et al., 2013), which could affect the rate of co-
932 localization between GA and NMDARs.

933 Regarding non-alanine substitutions in the GluN1 subunit, a previous study reported that
934 the GluN1-D732E/GluN2A receptor did not show altered surface expression while exhibiting a
935 ~1,796-fold increase in EC₅₀ value for glycine (Williams et al., 1996; Kenny et al., 2009),
936 consistently with our results showing no difference in surface expression and ~1,457-fold increase
937 of EC₅₀ value for glycine. In addition, our recent study reported that the pathogenic GluN1-S688Y
938 variant did not alter the surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2A receptor but increased the EC₅₀
939 values for glycine to 2,122 μM (Skrenkova et al., 2020), consistently with our novel data. In
940 addition, our electrophysiological data with the GluN1-D732N/GluN2A receptor (EC₅₀ values for
941 glycine increased <4,000-fold compared with our measurement of 6,745-fold) (Williams et al.,
942 1996; Seljeset et al., 2023) and the GluN1-D732W/GluN2A receptor (no current responses)
943 (Seljeset et al., 2023) are consistent with previous studies. Regarding the published data with
944 non-alanine substitutions in the GluN2A subunit, an earlier study reported a 50% decrease, and
945 we observed an 88% decrease in surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2A-R518H receptor (this

946 difference may be explained by the use of colorimetric versus microscopic assays). Neither study
947 detected current responses in HEK293 cells transfected with GluN1/GluN2A-R518H receptor
948 (Swanger et al., 2016). In addition, the pathogenic GluN2B-E413G variant reduced surface
949 expression of the GluN1/GluN2B receptor by ~82% percent and increased the EC₅₀ value for L-
950 glutamate by ~237-fold, which is consistent with our data with the GluN1/GluN2A-E413A receptor
951 showing 71% lower relative surface expression and ~288-fold higher EC₅₀ value for L-glutamate.
952 The mutant cycle of GluN1-S688 residue showed distinct levels of relative surface expression of
953 GluN1/GluN2A receptors that correlated with EC₅₀ value for glycine. Consistent with our data with
954 alanine substitutions, the surface expression levels of GluN1/GluN2A receptors containing the
955 mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue did not correlate with the EC₅₀ values for L-glutamate.
956 Our *in silico* analysis revealed a correlation between the relative surface expression values and
957 $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values as well as with the structural features represented by RMSD and SASA for the
958 GluN1-S688 residue mutant cycle. We hypothesize that the structural changes of LBD of the
959 GluN1 subunit, but not the functional properties, are the critical parameters sensed during the
960 early trafficking of the GluN1/GluN2A receptors. This is consistent with our observations that the
961 GluN1-D732E/GluN2A receptor was present on the cell surface similar to the WT GluN1/GluN2A
962 receptor but had a ~1,457-fold increased EC₅₀ value for glycine. The correlation between the
963 relative surface expression and the sensitivity of the LBD of the GluN1 subunit to glycine is in
964 agreement with our previous study with the GluN1/GluN3A receptor (Skrenkova et al., 2019). The
965 lack of correlation between the relative surface expression values and $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$, RMSD, and SASA
966 values observed with the GluN2A-S511 residue mutant cycle indicates the distinct mechanism
967 underlying the regulation of the early trafficking of the GluN1/GluN2A receptors containing the
968 mutations within the LBD of the GluN2A subunit compared with the GluN1 subunit. We also
969 suggest that the functional properties of the GluN1/GluN2A receptors containing the mutations
970 within the LBD of the GluN2A subunit are not critical parameters assessed during the ER
971 processing, as (i) the GluN1/GluN2A-S511A receptor showed a ~43% increase of surface
972 expression but a ~34-fold increased EC₅₀ value for L-glutamate, (ii) the GluN1/GluN2A-S511N
973 receptor showed regular surface expression but did not elicit any current responses in HEK293
974 cells. However, combining our experimental and *in silico* data with >80 mutant GluN1/GluN2
975 receptors has not enabled us to formulate a unified principle describing how the LBDs regulate
976 the ER release of GluN1/GluN2 receptors. We propose that future studies should include *in silico*
977 studies involving the full-length NMDARs.

978 Previous studies identified other regions in GluN subunits besides LBDs, including ATD
979 (Qiu et al., 2009), M3 domains (Horak et al., 2008), and CTDs (Standley et al., 2000; Scott et al.,

980 2001; Xia et al., 2001; Horak and Wenthold, 2009), containing ER retention and export signals.
981 We anticipate that future studies will investigate at what level other ER retention and export
982 signals contribute to regulating the surface expression of the GluN1/GluN2 receptors with mutated
983 LBDs. Further studies will also have to investigate the impact of the pathogenic variants in LBDs
984 of the GluN subunits during CNS development and postnatally.

985

986 **References**

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1215

1216 **Figure legends**

1217 **Figure 1.** Mutations of residues in the LBD of the GluN1 subunit that interact with glycine affect
1218 surface expression and glycine potency of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. **(A)** The structural model of
1219 the NMDAR comprises GluN1 (depicted in green) and GluN2A (depicted in red) subunits (based
1220 on PDB ID: 7EU7). **(B)** Structural model of the LBD of GluN1 subunit with labeled glycine-
1221 interacting amino acids (based on PDB ID: 1PB7). **(C)** Representative images of HEK293 cells
1222 transfected with either the YFP-GluN1-1a subunit (WT or mutant variant) alone (negative control)
1223 or with the GluN2A subunit. The total and surface signals (top and bottom row, respectively) of
1224 YFP-GluN1-1a subunits were labeled using an anti-GFP antibody 24 hours after the transfection.
1225 **(D,H)** Summary of the relative surface expression of NMDARs consisting of either WT or mutated
1226 YFP-GluN1-1a subunit co-expressed with the GluN2A subunit **(D)** and WT or mutated GluN1-4a
1227 subunit co-expressed with the GFP-GluN2A subunit **(H)**, measured using fluorescence
1228 microscopy; * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.010$ and*** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points
1229 correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 56$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(E)**
1230 Representative whole-cell patch-clamp recordings of HEK293 cells expressing the indicated GluN
1231 subunits. Glycine (gly) at the indicated concentrations was applied in the continuous presence of
1232 300 μ M L-glutamate (L-glu). **(F,I)** Normalized concentration-response curves for glycine
1233 measured from HEK293 cells expressing NMDARs containing YFP-GluN1-1a **(F)** or GluN1-4a
1234 subunit variants **(I)** co-expressed with the GluN2A subunit were obtained by fitting the data using
1235 *Equation (1)* (see Methods); for the summary of fitting parameters see **Table 1**. **(G,J)** Correlation
1236 of surface expression and glycine EC_{50} values at NMDARs composed of WT or mutated YFP-
1237 GluN1-1a subunit; **(G)** and WT or mutated GluN1-4a **(J)** subunit expressed together with GFP-
1238 GluN2A subunit; data were fitted by linear regression.

1239

1240 **Figure 2.** Mutations of residues in LBD of GluN2A subunit interacting with L-glutamate affect
1241 surface expression and L-glutamate potency of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. **(A)** Structural model of
1242 the LBD of the GluN2A subunit labeled with L-glutamate-interacting amino acids (based on PDB
1243 ID: 5I57). **(B)** Representative images of HEK293 cells co-transfected with WT GluN1-4a and WT

1244 or mutated GFP-GluN2A subunits. The total and surface signals (top and bottom row,
1245 respectively) of GFP- GluN2A subunits were labeled using an anti-GFP antibody 24 hours after
1246 the transfection. **(C)** Summary of the relative surface expression of NMDARs consisting of either
1247 WT or mutated GFP-GluN2A subunit together with WT GluN1-4a subunit, measured using
1248 fluorescence microscopy; * $p < 0.050$ and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points
1249 correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 136$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(D)**
1250 Representative whole-cell voltage-clamp recordings of HEK293 cells transfected with the
1251 indicated NMDAR subunits. L-glutamate (L-glu) at the indicated concentrations was applied in the
1252 continuous presence of 100 μ M glycine (gly). **(E)** Normalized concentration-response curves for
1253 L-glutamate measured from HEK293 cells expressing NMDARs containing WT or mutated GluN1-
1254 4a/GFP-GluN2A receptors were obtained by fitting the data using *Equation (1)* (see Methods) for
1255 the summary of fitting parameters see **Table 2**. **(F)** Correlation of surface expression and EC_{50}
1256 values for L-glutamate at NMDARs composed of WT or mutated GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A
1257 receptors; data were fitted by linear regression.

1258
1259 **Figure 3.** Alanine substitutions in the LBDs of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits alter the early
1260 trafficking of NMDARs. **(A)** Schematic representation of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct with
1261 a signal sequence (grey), conditional aggregation domain (orange), furin cleavage site (blue),
1262 mNEONGreen (green; mNEON sequence was inserted after the 21st amino acid residue of the
1263 GluN1-1a subunit (red)). Upon the addition of the ARIAD ligand (AL) to the cells, AL binds to the
1264 conditional aggregation domain, leading to a conformational change and release of the ARIAD-
1265 mNEON-GluN1-1a construct from the ER, followed by cleavage of the ARIAD sequence by the
1266 protease furin. See also the Materials and Methods section. **(B)** Representative images of
1267 HEK293 cells expressing ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct either alone or with the GluN2A
1268 subunit at 0 min (without AL) and 60 min after adding AL. The total and surface signals (top and
1269 bottom row, respectively) of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a constructs were labeled using an anti-
1270 mNEONGreen antibody 24 hours after the transfection. The representative images of GluN1-
1271 4a/ARIAD-mNEON-GluN2A receptor are shown in Figure S1. **(C)** Summary of relative surface
1272 expression of NMDARs containing WT or mutated ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a constructs together
1273 with GluN2A subunit in the absence or presence (60 min) of AL, measured using fluorescence
1274 microscopy; *** $p < 0.001$ for differences between ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A in the
1275 presence of AL and ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a expressed alone; +++ $p < 0.001$ for differences
1276 between presence and absence of AL; two-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual
1277 cells ($n \geq 26$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. See Figure S2A and Figure S2B for

1278 a summary of the relative surface expression of the time points for the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a
1279 construct co-expressed with GluN2A or GluN3A subunits. **(D)** Representative microscopy images
1280 of the HEK293 cells co-transfected with ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct and GluN2A or
1281 GluN3A subunits in the absence or presence (30 min) of AL; the anti-GM130 antibody was used
1282 to label the GA. **(E)** Summary of the average intensity of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunit signal
1283 co-localized with GM130 over the average intensity of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunit signal
1284 outside the GM130 signal, calculated for the indicated NMDAR combinations; *** $p < 0.001$ for
1285 differences between ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN3A receptors in presence of AL and ARIAD-
1286 mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors; ++ $p < 0.01$ for differences between presence and absence
1287 of AL; two-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 18$), and the red box plot
1288 represents mean \pm SEM. See Figure S3 for a summary of the time points for co-localized ARIAD-
1289 mNEON-GluN1-1a construct co-expressed with GluN2A subunits. **(F,G)** Summary of relative
1290 surface expression of NMDARs containing WT or mutated ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunits
1291 co-expressed with WT GluN2A subunit **(F)** or WT ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunit co-
1292 expressed with WT or mutated GluN2A subunit **(G)**, measured in the absence or presence (60
1293 min) of AL, using fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.010$, and *** $p < 0.001$ for differences between
1294 WT and mutated ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptors in presence of AL; +++ $p < 0.001$
1295 for differences between absence and presence of AL; two-way ANOVA. Data points correspond
1296 to individual cells ($n \geq 55$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. Different internalization
1297 rates did not affect the surface expression of GluN1/GluN2A-S511A receptors; see representative
1298 images of internalization assay with WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-
1299 S511A receptors (Figure S4A) and the subsequent quantification of surface and internalized GFP
1300 signals (Figure S4B).

1301
1302 **Figure 4.** Alanine substitutions in the LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A subunits additively or
1303 synergically regulate the early trafficking of GluN1/GluN2A receptors. **(A)** Summary of the relative
1304 surface expression of NMDARs containing mutations within LBDs of both GluN1-4a and GFP-
1305 GluN2A subunits, measured using fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT;
1306 one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 55$), and the red box plot
1307 represents mean \pm SEM. **(B,D,F)** Representative whole-cell patch-clamp recordings of GluN1-4a-
1308 N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C **(B)**, GluN1-4a-N499C-Q686C/GFP-GluN2A **(D)**,
1309 and GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-K487C-N687C **(F)** receptors expressed in the HEK293 cells. The
1310 current responses were elicited under the specified conditions. ECS denotes Mg^{2+} -free
1311 extracellular solution, L-glu represents L-glutamate (1 mM), and gly indicates glycine (1 mM). As

1312 indicated, 10 μ M 5,7-dichlorokynurenic acid (DCKA) and 50 μ M D-2-amino-5-
1313 phosphonopentanoate (D-APV) were applied. **(C,E,G)** Comparison of current response
1314 amplitudes evoked by ECS without Mg^{2+} **(C)**, 1 mM L-glutamate plus 10 μ M DCKA **(E)**, and 1 mM
1315 glycine plus 50 μ M D-APV **(G)**. **(H)** Summary of relative surface expression for NMDARs
1316 composed of GluN1-4a and GFP-GluN2A subunits with the closed cleft (CC) conformation of
1317 LBDs in combination with selected alanine substitutions, measured using fluorescence
1318 microscopy; *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells (n
1319 ≥ 54), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(I)** Representative whole-cell patch-clamp
1320 recordings from the HEK293 cells expressing the indicated GluN subunits. Glycine (gly) and/or L-
1321 glutamate (L-glu) were applied as indicated at a concentration of 1 mM, and 50 mM BME was
1322 applied 1 min before the second application of gly or L-glu. **(J)** Summary of the
1323 electrophysiological data analysis shown in I; the graph shows the percentage change of the peak
1324 current amplitudes induced by indicated combinations of (co-)agonists before and after BME
1325 treatment; CC indicates the closed cleft configuration of GluN1-4a or GluN2A subunits; *** $p <$
1326 0.001 vs the current response after BME treatment; two-way ANOVA. **(K)** Summary of the effect
1327 of indicated competitive antagonists on surface expression of WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A
1328 receptors, measured using fluorescence microscopy; $p > 0.05$; one-way ANOVA. The
1329 abbreviations are as follows: L-689,560, 4-trans-2-carboxy-5,7-dichloro-4-
1330 phenylaminocarbonylamino-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline; L-701,324, 7-chloro-4-hydroxy-3-(3-
1331 phenoxy)phenyl-2(1H)-quinolone; PEAQX, 5-phosphonomethyl-1,4-dihydroquinoxaline-2,3-
1332 dione; CPP, 4-(3-phosphonopropyl) piperazine-2-carboxylic acid. Data points correspond to
1333 individual cells ($n \geq 107$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM.

1334

1335 **Figure 5.** Alanine substitutions in LBDs cause similar changes in surface expression of
1336 GluN1/GluN2B receptors as we observed for GluN1/GluN2A receptors. **(A)** Summary of the
1337 relative surface expression of NMDARs consisting of either WT or mutated YFP-GluN1-1a
1338 subunits co-expressed with the GluN2B subunit, measured using fluorescence microscopy; *** p
1339 < 0.001 vs WT, one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 84$), and the red
1340 box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(B)** Correlation analysis of relative surface expression of YFP-
1341 GluN1-1a/GluN2A and YFP-GluN1-1a/GluN2B receptors. **(C)** Structural model of the LBD of the
1342 GluN2B subunit labeled with L-glutamate-interacting amino acids (based on PDB ID: 4PE5). **(D)**
1343 Summary of the relative surface expression of NMDARs consisting of either WT or mutated GFP-
1344 GluN2B subunit co-expressed with the WT GluN1-4a subunit, measured using fluorescence
1345 microscopy; * $p < 0.050$, ** $p < 0.010$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points

1346 correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 64$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(E)**
1347 Correlation analysis between relative surface expression levels of homologous mutations in
1348 GluN2A and GluN2B subunits when co-expressed with the WT GluN1-4a subunit. The plotted
1349 points in the graph were labeled according to the amino acid positions of the GluN2A subunit. For
1350 normalized concentration-response curves, see Figure S5, and for fitting parameters, see Table
1351 3. **(F)** Correlation analysis between EC_{50} values measured for WT and mutated GluN1/GluN2A
1352 and GluN1/GluN2B receptors. The plotted points in the graph were labeled according to the amino
1353 acid positions of the GluN2A subunit.

1354
1355 **Figure 6.** Pathogenic variants in LBDs of both GluN1 and GluN2A subunits affect the surface
1356 expression and agonist potency of NMDARs. **(A)** Representative images from HEK293 cells
1357 transfected with the WT or mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit either alone or with the hGluN2A
1358 subunit. The total and the surface signals (top and bottom row, respectively) of YFP-hGluN1-1a
1359 subunits were labeled using an anti-GFP antibody 24 hours after the transfection. **(B,C)** Summary
1360 of relative surface expression of YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing pathogenic
1361 variants within the LBDs of the YFP-hGluN1-1a **(B)** or hGluN2A **(C)** subunits, measured using
1362 fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.010$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs respective WT; one-way ANOVA. Data
1363 points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 16$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(D)**
1364 Representative whole-cell voltage-clamp recordings from HEK293 cells transfected with the
1365 indicated NMDAR subunits. Glycine (gly) at the indicated concentrations was applied in the
1366 continuous presence of 300 μ M L-glutamate (L-glu). **(E)** Normalized concentration-response
1367 curves for glycine measured from HEK293 cells expressing WT or mutated YFP-hGluN1-
1368 1a/hGluN2A receptors obtained by fitting the data using *Equation (1)* (see Methods); for the
1369 summary of fitting parameters, see **Table 5**.

1370
1371 **Figure 7.** Microscopical and electrophysiological characterization of the mutant cycles of the
1372 GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511 residues. **(A)** Summary of the relative surface expression of
1373 NMDARs containing the indicated mutations of the GluN1-S688 residue, measured using
1374 fluorescence microscopy; * $p < 0.050$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points
1375 correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 82$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(B)**
1376 Normalized concentration-response curves for glycine (gly) measured from HEK293 cells
1377 expressing WT and mutant NMDARs were obtained by fitting the data using *Equation (1)* (see
1378 Methods); for the summary of fitting parameters, see **Table 5**. **(C)** Correlation analysis of surface
1379 expression and EC_{50} values for glycine for WT and mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors

1380 containing the S688 residue mutant cycle variants; fitted by linear regression. For K_d value
1381 estimations, see Figure S6; for the correlation analysis of EC_{50} and K_d values for glycine, see
1382 Figure S7. **(D)** Summary of the relative surface expression of NMDARs containing the indicated
1383 mutations, measured using fluorescence microscopy; * $p < 0.050$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-
1384 way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 29$), and the red box plot represents
1385 mean \pm SEM. **(E)** Normalized concentration-response curves for L-glutamate (L-glu) measured
1386 from HEK293 cells expressing NMDARs containing mutations of the GluN2A-S511 residue
1387 obtained by fitting the data using *Equation (1)* (see Methods); for the summary of fitting
1388 parameters, see **Table 5**. **(F)** Correlation analysis of relative surface expression values and EC_{50}
1389 values for L-glutamate for WT and mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors fitted by linear
1390 regression. For K_d value estimations, see Figure S8; for the correlation analysis of EC_{50} and K_d
1391 values for L-glutamate, see Figure S9.

1392
1393 **Figure 8.** *In silico* analysis of the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511 residues.
1394 **(A,G)** The RMSD values were derived from 1 μ s-long atomistic simulations of the glycine (A) or
1395 L-glutamate (G) heavy atoms. These values were calculated by least-square fitting the structures
1396 to the backbone of the LBDs of either WT GluN1 or mutated GluN1 subunits at S688 residue
1397 position (A) and WT GluN2A or mutated GluN2A subunits at S511 residue position (G) (PDB ID:
1398 5KCJ). For RMSF values, see Figures S10 and S11. **(B,H)** The SASA values were derived from
1399 1 μ s-long atomistic simulations of the glycine (B) or L-glutamate (H) heavy atoms. These values
1400 were calculated by least-square fitting the structures to the backbone of the LBDs of either WT
1401 GluN1 or mutated GluN1 subunits at S688 residue position (B), and WT GluN2A or mutated
1402 GluN2A subunits at S511 residue position (H) (PDB: 5KCJ). **(C,I)** Correlation analysis between
1403 relative surface expression and RMSD values for the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 (C) or
1404 GluN2A-S511 (I) residues. The data were fitted by linear regression. For the summary of RMSD
1405 values, see **Table 6**. **(D,J)** Correlation analysis between relative surface expression and SASA
1406 values for the mutant cycles of the GluN1-S688 (D) or GluN2A-S511 (J) residues. The data were
1407 fitted by linear regression. For the summary of SASA values, see **Table 6**. **(E,K)** Correlation
1408 analysis between EC_{50} and $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for glycine for the mutant cycle of the GluN1-S688
1409 residue (E), or L-glutamate for the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue (K). The data were
1410 fitted by linear regression. For the summary of $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values, see **Table 6**. **(F,L)** Correlation
1411 analysis between relative surface expression and $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values for glycine for the mutant cycle
1412 of the GluN1-S688 residue (F) or L-glutamate for the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue

1413 (L). The data were fitted by linear regression. For the summary of EC_{50} values, see **Table 5**; for
1414 $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values, see **Table 6**.

1415
1416 **Figure 9.** The role of the pathogenic variants and other mutations in LBDs of both GluN1 and
1417 GluN2A subunits in the regulation of the surface expression of NMDARs. **(A)** Representative
1418 images of HEK293 cells expressing ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a construct either alone or with the
1419 GluN2A subunit at 0 min (without AL) and 60 min after adding AL. The total and surface signals
1420 (top and bottom row, respectively) of ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a subunits were labeled using an
1421 anti-mNEONGreen antibody 24 hours after the transfection. **(B,C)** Summary of relative surface
1422 expression of NMDARs containing WT or mutated ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a subunits co-
1423 expressed together with WT hGluN2A subunit **(B)** or WT ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a subunit co-
1424 expressed with WT or mutated hGluN2A subunits **(C)** measured in the absence or presence (60
1425 min) of AL, using fluorescence microscopy; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.010$, and *** $p < 0.001$ for differences
1426 between ARIAD-mNEON-hGluN1-1a/GluN2A receptor and mutated NMDARs in presence of AL;
1427 +*** $p < 0.001$ for differences between absence and presence of AL; two-way ANOVA. Data points
1428 correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 54$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(D,E,F)**
1429 Summary of the relative surface expression of NMDARs containing mutations within LBDs of
1430 YFP-hGluN1-1a and hGluN2A subunits, measured using fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.01$,
1431 and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 81$), and
1432 the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(G,H)** Summary of relative surface expression for
1433 NMDARs composed of GluN1-4a and GFP-GluN2A subunits with the closed cleft (CC)
1434 conformation of LBDs in combination with selected substitutions, measured using fluorescence
1435 microscopy; * $p < 0.05$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to
1436 individual cells ($n \geq 67$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM.

1437
1438 **Figure 10.** Microscopical analysis of the selected mutations of the GluN1-S688 and GluN2A-S511
1439 residues in hippocampal neurons. **(A)** Representative images of hippocampal neurons
1440 transfected with the WT or mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a subunits. The total and the surface signal
1441 (top and bottom row, respectively) of YFP-GluN1-1a subunits were labeled using an anti-GFP
1442 antibody 48 hours after the transfection. **(B)** Summary of the relative surface expression of YFP-
1443 hGluN1-1a subunits mutated at the S688 residue position, expressed in hippocampal neurons
1444 determined using fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.010$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way
1445 ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual segments ($n \geq 46$), and the red box plot represents
1446 mean \pm SEM. **(C)** Summary of the relative surface expression of WT YFP-hGluN1-1a alone or co-

1447 transfected with the WT hGluN2A subunit expressed in hippocampal neurons determined using
 1448 fluorescence microscopy; *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; Student's t -test. Data points correspond to
 1449 individual segments ($n \geq 38$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM. **(D)** Summary of the
 1450 relative surface expression of WT YFP-hGluN1-1a subunit co-transfected with WT or mutated
 1451 hGluN2A subunits at the S511 residue position, expressed in hippocampal neurons determined
 1452 using fluorescence microscopy; ** $p < 0.010$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs WT; one-way ANOVA. Data
 1453 points correspond to individual segments ($n \geq 42$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM.
 1454

1455 Tables

1456 **Table 1.** Summary of fitting parameters for steady-state concentration-response curves for
 1457 glycine measured in HEK293 cells expressing the indicated NMDAR subunits carrying a mutation
 1458 in the LBD of the GluN1 subunit.

Receptor	EC ₅₀ (μ M)	I _{max}	h	n	Receptor	EC ₅₀ (μ M)	I _{max}	h	n
YFP-GluN1-1a/ GluN2A	2.40 \pm 0.23	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.41 \pm 0.03	5	GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A	2.27 \pm 0.26	1.06 \pm 0.03	1.31 \pm 0.15	8
YFP-GluN1-1a-Q405A/ GluN2A	1.75 \pm 0.34	1.01 \pm 0.02	1.04 \pm 0.08	8	GluN1-4a- Q405A/ GFP-GluN2A	1.87 \pm 0.36	1.10 \pm 0.03	0.95 \pm 0.09	5
YFP-GluN1-1a-F484A/ GluN2A	3,624.55 \pm 787.45	1.23 \pm 0.06	1.50 \pm 0.13	4	GluN1-4a- F484A/ GFP-GluN2A	4,897.02 \pm 512.26	1.30 \pm 0.08	1.62 \pm 0.14	6
YFP-GluN1-1a-P516A/ GluN2A	20.61 \pm 1.38	1.07 \pm 0.02	1.29 \pm 0.04	7	GluN1-4a- P516A/ GFP-GluN2A	17.87 \pm 1.77	1.02 \pm 0.01	1.25 \pm 0.05	9
YFP-GluN1-1a-T518A/ GluN2A	640.72 \pm 63.64	1.01 \pm 0.00	1.44 \pm 0.03	7	GluN1-4a- T518A/ GFP-GluN2A	533.11 \pm 62.20	1.02 \pm 0.01	1.36 \pm 0.06	8
YFP-GluN1-1a-R523A/ GluN2A	10,261.34 \pm 1,052.06	2.02 \pm 0.13	1.31 \pm 0.08	4	GluN1-4a- R523A/ GFP-GluN2A	9,451.12 \pm 886.52	1.92 \pm 0.14	1.61 \pm 0.10	5
YFP-GluN1-1a-S688A/ GluN2A	5.48 \pm 0.56	1.03 \pm 0.01	1.32 \pm 0.06	5	GluN1-4a- S688A/ GFP-GluN2A	4.12 \pm 0.35	1.13 \pm 0.04	1.03 \pm 0.08	7
YFP-GluN1-1a-W731A/ GluN2A	2,824.15 \pm 183.58	1.14 \pm 0.02	1.61 \pm 0.07	5	GluN1-4a- W731A/ GFP-GluN2A	3,296.95 \pm 165.39	1.14 \pm 0.01	1.72 \pm 0.02	6
YFP-GluN1-1a-D732A/ GluN2A	NR	-	-	12	GluN1-4a- D732A/ GFP-GluN2A	NA	-	-	10

1459 The EC₅₀, I_{max} and h values were obtained by fitting the data from individual cells to *Equation (1)*.
 1460 There was no difference between the YFP-GluN1-1a and GluN1-4a versions; $p > 0.050$, Student's
 1461 t -test. NR indicates "not responding", and NA indicates "not analyzed".

1462

1463 **Table 2.** Summary of fitting parameters for steady-state concentration-response curves for L-
 1464 glutamate effect measured in HEK293 cells expressing the indicated NMDAR subunits carrying
 1465 a mutation in the LBD of GluN2A subunit.

Receptor	EC ₅₀ (μM)	I _{max}	<i>h</i>	<i>n</i>
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A	6.10 ± 0.70	0.96 ± 0.01	1.34 ± 0.04	5
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-E413A	1,754.81 ± 114.61	1.11 ± 0.01	1.27 ± 0.05	6
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-H485A	3,969.98 ± 253.57	1.25 ± 0.03	1.50 ± 0.04	6
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-S511A	235.41 ± 18.32	1.00 ± 0.02	1.35 ± 0.03	6
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-T513A	809.56 ± 109.74	1.02 ± 0.01	1.33 ± 0.03	5
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-R518A	8,895.17 ± 1,702.60	1.83 ± 0.29	1.96 ± 0.15	5
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-S689A	7.42 ± 0.82	1.01 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.05	5
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-T690A	5,254.10 ± 339.72	1.40 ± 0.04	1.45 ± 0.05	7
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-Y730A	2,099.49 ± 170.86	1.09 ± 0.02	1.58 ± 0.07	6
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2A-Y761A	3,542.66 ± 173.32	1.20 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.10	8

1466 The EC₅₀, I_{max} and *h* values were obtained by fitting the data from individual cells to *Equation (1)*.

1467

1468 **Table 3.** Summary of fitting parameters for steady-state concentration-response curves for L-
 1469 glutamate measured in HEK293 cells expressing the indicated GluN1/GluN2B receptors.

Receptor	EC ₅₀ (μM)	I _{max}	<i>h</i>	<i>n</i>
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B	1.46 ± 0.07	0.98 ± 0.01	1.22 ± 0.07	9
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-S512A	12.80 ± 1.57	1.01 ± 0.00	1.43 ± 0.06	6
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-T514A	118.58 ± 4.97	1.06 ± 0.00	1.14 ± 0.03	7
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-R519A	1,562.84 ± 263.28	1.08 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.07	4
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-T691A	867.10 ± 124.90	1.04 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.06	5
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-Y731A	324.94 ± 9.68	1.03 ± 0.01	1.19 ± 0.03	9
GluN1-4a/ GFP-GluN2B-Y762A	3,053.74 ± 155.64	1.24 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.05	5

1470 The EC₅₀, I_{max} and *h* values were obtained by fitting the data from individual cells to *Equation (1)*.

1471

1472 **Table 4.** Pathogenic and potential pathogenic variants in LBDs of GluN1 and GluN2A investigated
1473 in this study.

Variant	Gene	Genotype	Phenotype	References
GluN1-R523C	<i>GRIN1</i>	c.1567C >T	DA	(Kalbaugh et al., 2004); ClinVar ID: 1308763
GluN1-S688Y	<i>GRIN1</i>	c.2063C >A	Early infantile encephalopathy, Intellectual disability	(Zehavi et al., 2017; Skrenkova et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023); ClinVar ID: 981272
GluN1-S688P	<i>GRIN1</i>	c.2062T >C	DA	ClinVar ID: 429761
GluN1-D732E	<i>GRIN1</i>	-	DA	(Santos-Gómez et al., 2021)
GluN2A-S511L	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.1532C >T	Landau-Kleffner syndrome	ClinVar ID: 80290
GluN2A-T513I	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.1538C >T	Landau-Kleffner syndrome	ClinVar ID: 424392
GluN2A-R518C	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.1552C >T	Landau-Kleffner syndrome	(Strehlow et al., 2019); ClinVar ID: 205687
GluN2A-R518H	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.1553G >A	Landau-Kleffner syndrome	(Lesca et al., 2013; Conroy et al., 2014; Swanger et al., 2016; Strehlow et al., 2019); ClinVar ID: 88732
GluN2A-R518L	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.1553G >T	Landau-Kleffner syndrome	ClinVar ID: 567708
GluN2A-T690M	<i>GRIN2</i> A	c.2069C >T	Inborn genetic diseases, Landau-Kleffner syndrome, neurodevelopmental disorder	(Nykamp et al., 2017; Fernández-Marmiesse et al., 2019); ClinVar ID: 444362

1474

1475 The variants were selected from the open-source GRIN database
 1476 (<https://alf06.uab.es/grindb/home>). The information provided is current as of January 1, 2022.
 1477 Variants marked as 'DA' denote disease-associated or potential pathogenic variants.

1478

1479 **Table 5.** Summary of fitting parameters for steady-state concentration-response curves for
 1480 glycine and L-glutamate measured in HEK293 cells expressing the human versions of the
 1481 GluN1/GluN2A receptors carrying the indicated pathogenic variants and the mutant cycle
 1482 substitutions.

Receptor	Agonist	EC ₅₀ (μM)	I _{max}	<i>h</i>	<i>n</i>
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A	glycine	2.96 ± 0.29	1.01 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.08	6
YFP-hGluN1-1a-R523C/ hGluN2A	glycine	NR	-	-	10
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688A/ hGluN2A	glycine	5.02 ± 0.75	1.04 ± 0.1	0.96 ± 0.04	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688Y/ hGluN2A	glycine	2,795.62 ± 787.88	1.26 ± 0.09	1.12 ± 0.11	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/ hGluN2A	glycine	9,435.59 ± 1,533.21	1.93 ± 0.15	0.96 (Fixed)	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688C/ hGluN2A	glycine	26.88 ± 5.07	0.99 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.07	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688N/ hGluN2A	glycine	147.66 ± 9.17	1.02 ± 0.00	1.38 ± 0.08	7
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688E/ hGluN2A	glycine	3,044.67 ± 496.54	1.18 ± 0.04	1.49 ± 0.15	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688K/ hGluN2A	glycine	NA*	-	-	>6 0
YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688W/ hGluN2A	glycine	2,249.31 ± 105.92	1.11 ± 0.01	1.49 ± 0.04	8
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A	L-glutamate	5.31 ± 0.88	0.99 ± 0.01	1.28 ± 0.04	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511L	L-glutamate	NR	-	-	11
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511A	L-glutamate	179.45 ± 29.45	1.00 ± 0.00	1.05 ± 0.02	5

YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511P	L-glutamate	67.71 ± 8.08	0.96 ± 0.00	1.14 ± 0.04	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511C	L-glutamate	264.49 ± 38.94	1.00 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.04	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511N	L-glutamate	NR	-	-	8
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511E	L-glutamate	342.32 ± 61.05	1.02 ± 0.01	1.13 ± 0.06	6
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511K	L-glutamate	NR	-	-	8
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511W	L-glutamate	NR	-	-	5

1483 The EC₅₀, I_{max} and *h* values were obtained by fitting the data from individual cells to Equation (1).
1484 NR indicates “not responding,” and NA indicates “not analyzed”. *In initial experiments with the
1485 GluN1-S688K/GluN2A receptor, we observed current responses in the range of 466-877 pA (n =
1486 6), but we could not later replicate these results when validating our electrophysiological data
1487 during the revisions. For corresponding *K_d* values and fitting parameters, see Table S1.

1488

1489 **Table 6.** Summary of RMSD, SASA, and Δ*G*_{binding} values for LBDs of the GluN1 subunit for glycine
1490 and the GluN2A subunit for L-glutamate obtained by MD simulations.

LBD	Agonist	RMSD [Å]	SASA [Å ²]	Δ <i>G</i> _{binding} [kcal/mol]
hGluN1	glycine	2.31 ± 0.01	14,217.90 ± 14.26	-32.18 ± 1.35
hGluN1-S688A	glycine	3.42 ± 0.03	14,747.81 ± 21.12	-25.02 ± 2.14
hGluN1-S688Y	glycine	2.10 ± 0.02	14,321.65 ± 20.05	-33.27 ± 3.10
hGluN1-S688P	glycine	6.79 ± 0.11	15,330.34 ± 16.80	-7.21 ± 3.77
hGluN1-S688C	glycine	2.36 ± 0.02	14,343.69 ± 18.10	-30.27 ± 1.86
hGluN1-S688N	glycine	4.11 ± 0.01	13,783.14 ± 16.53	-34.84 ± 1.30
hGluN1-S688E	glycine	2.71 ± 0.02	14,130.32 ± 13.76	-23.80 ± 2.31
hGluN1-S688K	glycine	9.55 ± 0.10	15,723.66 ± 17.28	-1.84 ± 2.35
hGluN1-S688W	glycine	5.32 ± 0.03	14,988.77 ± 21.89	-29.33 ± 3.22

hGluN2A	L-glutamate	2.28 ± 0.01	14,596.85 ± 13.91	-36.50 ± 2.95
hGluN2A-S511L	L-glutamate	2.97 ± 0.01	14,398.11 ± 13.23	-31.31 ± 2.00
hGluN2A-S511A	L-glutamate	2.74 ± 0.02	14,542.83 ± 15.59	-34.81 ± 2.15
hGluN2A-S511P	L-glutamate	2.06 ± 0.01	14,263.28 ± 14.01	-43.01 ± 1.81
hGluN2A-S511C	L-glutamate	3.88 ± 0.02	15,237.64 ± 13.77	-11.76 ± 5.14
hGluN2A-S511N	L-glutamate	3.49 ± 0.02	14,978.40 ± 14.27	-4.75 ± 3.75
hGluN2A-S511E	L-glutamate	2.57 ± 0.02	14,547.50 ± 12.73	-25.37 ± 3.64
hGluN2A-S511K	L-glutamate	4.20 ± 0.02	14,954.19 ± 13.85	-3.85 ± 3.13
hGluN2A-S511W	L-glutamate	3.32 ± 0.02	14,946.35 ± 15.09	-17.42 ± 5.21

1491 RMSD and SASA values were calculated from the last 500 ns of the 1 μ s-long simulation for each LBD
1492 structure; see Materials and Methods section for more details.

1493

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

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Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

